

Carbon-Chalcogen Coupling Reactions: Efforts toward the Synthesis of Diaryl Chalcogenides and Chalcogenyl Heterocycles

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the award of the degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

by

Ch. Durga Prasad

1110203

to the

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY

**INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION AND
RESEARCH BHOPAL**

Bhopal – 462 066

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CERTIFICATE

The undersigned have examined the Ph.D. thesis entitled:

Carbon-Chalcogen Coupling Reactions: Efforts toward the Synthesis of Diaryl Chalcogenides and Chalcogenyl Heterocycles

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DEDICATION

To

my parents

*(for their understanding, emotional support, blessings and
prayers throughout my life)*

ABSTRACT

This thesis reports the synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides and various chalcogenyl heterocycles using carbon-chalcogen coupling reactions. The formation of carbon-chalcogen (S/Se/Te) bond is one of the fundamental reactions in synthetic chemistry of main group compounds and represents a key step for the construction of a broad range of organic molecules, which are of paramount importance in drugs, functional materials, and metal complexes. The construction of carbon-chalcogen bond by an atom-economical and environmentally benign conditions is always desirable. Unsymmetrical diaryl chalcogenides are ubiquitous structural motifs in numerous biologically active natural products, pharmaceuticals, and materials. Therefore, the synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides has attracted considerable interest. In this thesis, I have discussed a general method where dichalcogenides reacted with arenes to form respective diaryl chalcogenides. This method was remarkable in terms of synthesis of various monochalcogenides. It was extended with slight modifications, to synthesize 3-sulfenyl indole, a functionality that exists in a variety of natural products and synthetic drugs and plays a significant role in medicinal chemistry. Further, 2,3-bis sulfenyl indoles have also been obtained.

Synthesis of various chalcogenyl heterocycles from diaryl dichalcogenides

Benzothiazine is considered as a promising unit in the field of pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals. A silver mediated two step methodology has been presented for the synthesis of benzothiazines from unactivated alkenes. Functionalized oxindoles have elicited significant synthetic interest because of their important applications in asymmetric synthesis, library design and drug discovery. A simple method has been demonstrated that involves direct sp^3 C-H functionalization to access diverse chalcogenyl heterocycles such as 3-sulfonyl oxindoles, sulfenyl and selenenyl heterocycles.

Keywords: Organochalcogens - C-S/Se coupling - Dichalcogenides - Heterocycles

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List of Symbols & Abbreviations

BSA	<i>N, O</i> -bis(trimethylsilylacetamide)
CCDC	Cambridge crystallographic data centre
dba	Dibenzylideneacetone
DMF	<i>N, N</i> -Dimethylformamide
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
<i>ee</i>	Enantiomeric excess
ESI	Electrospray ionization
ESMS	Electron spray mass spectrum
Equiv	Equivalent
G. F.	Goodness of fit
HRMS	High-resolution mass spectrum
LRMS	Low resolution mass spectrum
mL	Millilitre
mmol	Millimoles
MHz	Megahertz
Mp	Melting point
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
ORTEP	Oak Ridge thermal ellipsoid plot
Q-TOF	Quadrupole time-of-flight
THF	Tetrahydrofuran
TLC	Thin layer chromatography
UV	Ultraviolet
ρ	Density
μ	Absorption coefficient
<i>h, k, l</i>	Miller indices
α, β, γ	Unit cell angles
<i>a, b, c</i>	Unit cell lengths
h	Hours

CHAPTER 1

Introduction: Organochalcogens

1.1. Chalcogens

The term "chalcogens" was derived from the Greek word *chalcos*, meaning "ore formers," since they all are found in copper ores.¹ Their compounds are generally called as "chalcogenides." They were placed under the group 16 of the periodic table (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Chalcogens (Group 16 elements of the periodic table)

Oxygen was first discovered as an element by Carl Wilhelm Scheele in 1772 and it is a highly reactive non-metal and oxidizing agent that readily forms oxides with most elements as well as other compounds.² By mass, oxygen is the third-most abundant element in the universe, after hydrogen and helium. First time sulfur was recognized as an element by Antoine Lavoisier in 1777. Sulfur has twenty five naturally occurring isotopes; out of these, only four are stable with mass numbers 32, 33, 34 and 36.³ The element selenium was discovered by Jöns Jacob Berzelius in 1818.⁴ It was named after moon (*selênê* in Greek), while tellurium had been named after planet earth (*tellus* in Latin) and discovered by Franz-Joseph Müller von Reichenstein in 1782.⁵ Selenium has similar properties like tellurium (discovered some 35 years earlier) and the same is true with the organoselenium/organotellurium compounds (*vide infra*). Polonium was discovered in 1898 by Marie and Pierre Curie. It's a rare and highly radioactive element with no stable isotopes; polonium is chemically similar to bismuth and tellurium, and it occurs in uranium ores.⁶

Sulfur, selenium and tellurium can exist in different oxidation states such as -2, 0, +2, +4, +6. The most common oxidation state of S, Se and Te is +2. Uptake of O₂ from the air is the essential purpose of respiration; so oxygen supplementation is used in medicine. Elemental sulfur is used for the production of sulfuric acid and vulcanization of rubber,⁷ while elemental selenium for the production of glass. Selenium is used in the toning of photographic prints, and it is sold as a toner by numerous photographic manufacturers. Selenium intensifies and extends the tonal range of black-and-white photographic images

and improves the permanence of prints.^{6,7} The largest consumer of tellurium is metallurgy, where it is used in iron, copper and lead alloys. It has also applications in semiconductor and electronics industry.⁸

1.2. Brief history of organochalcogens (S, Se, Te)

The compounds containing carbon-chalcogen (S, Se, Te) bond are called organochalcogens. The first organosulfur compound, ethanethiol, was prepared by Zeise in 1834.⁹ The first organoselenium compound, diethyl selenide, was prepared by Löwig in 1836,¹⁰ while the corresponding first organic derivative of tellurium, diethyl telluride, was prepared by Wöhler in 1840.¹¹ These aliphatic organochalcogen compounds have limited scope because of their repulsive odours, high volatility, difficulties in purification and instability. In 1970, the discovery of several useful new reactions and a variety of novel structures with unusual properties began to attract more general interest in the discipline of organochalcogen chemistry. It was found that the aryl substituted derivatives of organochalcogens were less volatile and less offensive to handle than the original aliphatic compounds and that even the latter were relatively easy to manipulate by modern techniques.

Organosulfur compounds, a subclass of organic substances that contain sulfur and that are known for their varied occurrence and unusual properties. They are found in diverse locations, including in interstellar space, inside hot acidic volcanoes, and deep within the oceans. They even present in the bodies of all living organisms in the form of proteins, enzymes, vitamins and hormones. They are useful in general synthetic chemistry, pharmaceuticals, material science and food industry.¹² They are prevalent in natural products such as biotin, insulin, oxytocin, α -lipoic acid and drugs like penicillin, cephalosporin, seroquel, (-)-acetylaranotin etc. They are available in common edible foods such as onion, broccoli, garlic, radish, mushrooms, coffee etc.¹³ (Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.2: Common edible foods containing organosulfur compounds

Certain simple organosulfur compounds, such as thiols, are repugnant to humans and some animals even at extraordinarily low concentrations; they are used as defensive secretions by

a variety of animal species and figure in unpleasant odours associated with polluted air and water, particularly that resulting from the use of sulfur-rich fossil fuels.¹⁴

Organoselenium compounds have found such wide utility because of their effects on an extraordinary number of different reactions, including carbon-carbon bond formations, under relatively mild reaction conditions. Furthermore, organoselenium compounds can usually be used in presence of a wide variety of functional groups, thus avoiding protection group chemistry.¹⁵ Selenium group can be introduced in an organic substrate *via* both electrophilic and nucleophilic reagents. Organoselenium anions are powerful nucleophiles and usually they are prepared *in situ* because of their sensitivity to air oxidation.¹⁶ Moreover organochalcogens play an important role in synthetic chemistry, acting as versatile reagents in advanced synthesis and catalysis. Thus, they can be effectively introduced, manipulated and removed in a variety of ways.^{15c}

The advance in the area of synthesis and reactivity of organoselenium and tellurium compounds, as well as the discovery of the toxic properties of selenium compounds in 1930s and the subsequent discovery that selenium as an essential trace element in the diet, has prompted intense studies of the biological properties of both organic and inorganic selenium compounds.¹⁷ The biological and medicinal properties of organochalcogen (Se, Te) compounds are also increasingly appreciated, mainly due to their antioxidant, antitumor, antimicrobial, anticancer, and antiviral properties.¹⁸

Organotellurium compounds have many synthetic applications in organic chemistry as reagents. They have glutathione peroxidase (antioxidant) and chemo preventive (antitumor) activities. They play a significant role in biological, polymer and material sciences.¹⁹ Organotellurium chemistry is a very broad and exciting field with many opportunities for research and development of applications. Regarding the odour, toxicity, and instability, no highly specialized techniques are required in the handling of organotellurium compounds and work with these compounds is very similar to work with any other class of chemical compounds such as organoselenium, organosulfur, organotin, and organophosphorus compounds. The organotellurium group can be easily introduced into a variety of organic substrates by either nucleophilic or electrophilic tellurium species.²⁰

1.3. Applications of organochalcogen compounds

Organochalcogen compounds have many applications in general synthesis, biological, food and material sciences etc. They play a vital role as catalysts, synthetic intermediates and reagents in synthetic chemistry. Also they can be implied as ligands in transition-metal catalysis. Some of the compounds show the biological activity such as anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor and antioxidants. Hence, they are the composites of several pharmaceuticals and medicines. Moreover, on the other hand, sulfur-, selenium-, and tellurium derived organochalcogens have emerged as potential sensors for the detection of reactive oxygen species (ROS), reactive nitrogen species (RNS), and biothiols in recent years.²¹ The strong electron-donor ability of selenium has led to the synthesis of many transition metal complexes of organoselenium ligands, which have been found as promising catalysts for various organic transformations.²² Further, organochalcogen compounds act as intermediates in the synthesis of various complex heterocycles.²³

1.3.1. Organochalcogens as ligands

Organochalcogen compounds constitute an interesting and efficient class of ligands that can be used in the metal-catalyzed asymmetric reactions and it emerged as a new area of research for the scientists. Organosulfur compounds such as aryl sulfides are important intermediates and ligands in synthetic chemistry.²⁴ Various research groups have made significant progress in this field. Sulfur along with phosphorus forms chiral P, S hybrid ligands that have been used widely in asymmetric catalysis.²⁵

Scheme 1.1: Pd-catalyzed asymmetric decarboxylative cycloaddition

Xiao et al. have described the asymmetric decarboxylative cycloaddition reaction using chiral P, S hybrid ligand (Scheme 1.1).²⁶ Compound **1.4** is the new chiral hybrid P, S ligand which was exploited by combining a chiral β -amino sulfide and a simple diphenyl phosphite. The resultant ligand performed extremely well in a palladium catalyzed asymmetric decarboxylative [4+2] cycloaddition (ADC) reaction, thus generating multiple contiguous stereocenters and a chiral quaternary center. By doing so, a straightforward route

to highly functionalized tetrahydroquinolines (**1.3**) was developed with the yields up to 99%, as well as 98% *ee* and greater than 95:5 diastereomeric ratio.

Scheme 1.2: Pd-catalyzed asymmetric allylic alkylation

Braga and co-workers have described the synthesis of chiral β -seleno amide (**1.8**), via the ring-opening reaction of chiral 2-oxazolines by selenium nucleophiles and utilized as a ligand in the palladium-catalyzed asymmetric allylic alkylation (AAA) reaction between diphenyl acetoxy propene (**1.5**) and dimethyl malonate (**1.6**) to get alkylated product (**1.7**) upto 98% *ee* (Scheme 1.2).²⁷

1.3.2. Organochalcogens as synthetic intermediates

Organochalcogens act as versatile synthetic intermediates.²⁸ A practical and efficient synthesis for various β -ketoesters, including those which are α -substituted, was described by Rapoport and co-workers (Scheme 1.3).²⁹

Scheme 1.3: Synthesis of β -ketoesters through sulfide contraction

The α -thioiminium salt (**1.10**) prepared from a thioamide (**1.9**) and a primary or secondary alkylating agent was subjected to sulfur extrusion upon addition of a base and dichlorophenylphosphine, resulted in an enamino ester (**1.12**) through intermediate (**1.10**) which may be hydrolyzed to the desired β -keto ester (**1.13**). The method was also applicable to the preparation of various substituted β -keto nitriles.

Scheme 1.4: Synthesis of selenoiminium salts and their conversion to other products

In other reaction, Murai and co-workers have postulated selenoiminium salts to be putative intermediates.³⁰ A variety of selenoiminium salts (**1.15**) were obtained by reacting the corresponding selenoamides (**1.14**) with methyl triflate at room temperature for 30 seconds. All of the salts were stable under air. To examine the reactivity of the isolated selenoiminium intermediate, it was reacted with *n*-butyllithium to give two types of ketones (**1.16** and **1.17**). In a reaction with LiAlH₄/Te, the selenoiminium salts were converted to telluroamides (**1.18**) (Scheme 1.4).

Scheme 1.5: Reduction of cyclohexanonyl tellurium intermediate

Organotellurium compounds also act as synthetic intermediates. In 1980, Clive et al. reported a reaction where phenyl tellurium compound was used as the intermediate.³¹ Oxiranyl cyclohexanone (**1.19**), reacted with phenyl telluride ion to form tellurium intermediate (**1.20**), which on reduction with triphenyl tinhydride forms an alcoholic compound **1.21** (Scheme 1.5).

1.3.3. Organochalcogens as catalysts

Organochalcogen compounds were used as catalysts in many organic transformations. Organochalcogens play an important role as catalysts for epoxidation, oxidation and chloroamidation etc.³² Oxidation reactions are important and essential chemical processes. These reactions require proper organic or inorganic oxidants. Organochalcogen compounds, particularly, of selenium and tellurium, exhibit variable oxidation states and, therefore, has

been utilized as catalysts in several oxidation reactions.³³ They can be even designed in such a way that they catalyze asymmetric transformations.

Scheme 1.6: Aryl butylselenide catalyzed epoxidation of alkenes

Knochel and co-workers have demonstrated the epoxidation of various olefins with hydrogen peroxide in a fluoruous biphasic system by using 2,4-bis(perfluorooctyl)phenyl butylselenide (**1.23**) as catalyst.³⁴ The catalyst was soluble only in perfluorinated solvents and can easily be recovered simply by phase separation. Furthermore, the catalyst can be reused several times without affecting its catalytic efficiency (Scheme 1.6).

Scheme 1.7: Regioselective synthesis of medium-sized halolactones and bromooxepanes

Recently, our group has reported symmetrical bis(*p*-anisyl)selenide (**1.26**) catalyzed bromo/iodo lactonization of linear alkenoic acids (**1.25**) with *N*-bromo succinimide where 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) was used as co-catalyst and NaHCO₃ was used as an additive.³⁵ A series of medium-sized bromo/iodo lactones (**1.27**) possessing high transannular strain, were synthesized regioselectively. ⁷⁷Se NMR, HRMS and theoretical studies revealed that reaction proceeds through selenium-DMAP active catalyst (Scheme 1.7).

Scheme 1.8: Reduction of α -selenophenyl carboxylic esters using tellurium catalyst

Comasseto et al. have explored dithienyl ditelluride (**1.29**) catalyzed reduction of α -selenophenyl carboxylic esters and diethyl α -selenophenyl malonates (**1.28**) into corresponding selenofree carboxylic acids (**1.30**).³⁶ Sodium borohydride and aqueous sodium hydroxide were used to carry out the reduction in ethanol (Scheme 1.8).

1.3.4. Organochalcogens as reactants

There exists a plethora of reactions where organochalcogens act as reactants or coupling partners. Indeed, the very formation of carbon-chalcogen bond in a reaction is the process which involves organochalcogens as the reactants. There are many sources available in the literature, from where organosulfur moiety can be derived. These sources are generally commercially available; however, some of them should be synthesized from the simple precursors. A few of the commonly used organosulfur sources are thiols, disulfides, sulfonyl halides, sulfinic acids, sodium sulfinates, thiourea, aryl thiocyanates, arylsulfonyl cyanides and *N*-(thio)succinimides.³⁷ Elemental sulfur powder has been used for installing organosulfur moiety.³⁸ Inorganic sulfur salts such as sodium thiosulfate, potassium thiocyanate, sodium and potassium sulfides etc. can be used as sulfurating agents.³⁹

The available sources for incorporating organoselenium moiety are selenium powder, diaryl diselenides, organoselenenyl halides, enyne selenides, potassium seleno cyanate, selenenyl metallic reagents such as lithium areneselenolates (ArSeLi), tributyltin aryl selenides (ArSeSnBu₃) etc.⁴⁰ Similarly, the sources of organotellurium motif are tellurium powder, diaryl ditelluride, tellurium tetrachloride, telluro esters (ArTeCoAr') etc.⁴¹

1.4. Modes of construction of carbon-chalcogen bond

Actually, in literature there are five modes available for the formation of carbon-chalcogen bond.⁴² These modes can be categorized as the following types.

1. Coupling of organohalides with chalcogenyl metallic reagents
2. Transition metal catalyzed/mediated coupling of organohalides with organochalcogens
3. Transition metal catalyzed/mediated C-H bond activation
4. Transition metal free direct C-H bond functionalization
5. Decarboxylative approach

The first method was conventional in type, as it involves the usage of chalcogenyl metallic reagents, which must be prepared from organometallic reagents for the formation of carbon-chalcogen bond. Out of these methods, Transition metal catalyzed/mediated coupling

method has received much attention. It has been widely used for the construction of carbon-chalcogen bonds. Moreover, transition metal catalyzed/mediated coupling of chalcogenyl metallic reagents with organo halides/alkynes has also been used for the formation of organochalcogens.⁴³ Transition metal catalyzed/mediated C-H bond activation has emerged as other successful method for the formation of carbon-chalcogen bond in an atom-economic way. Recently, transition metal free direct C-H functionalization has become the most amenable method for the construction of carbon-chalcogen bond, based on the view of removal of toxic metals in pharmaceutical field of research. Another approach was decarboxylative coupling method, which provides an alternative access to carbon-chalcogen bond without the need for halocarbon precursors.^{42b}

1.4.1. Coupling of organohalides with chalcogenyl metallic reagents

Organohalides such as alkyl or aryl halides reacted with chalcogenyl metallic reagents like sodium and lithium chalcogenides, chalcogenyl magnesium bromides, tributyl tin chalcogenides to form respective organochalcogen compounds. These reagents are difficult to prepare and handling of them needs special safety precautions. General pictorial representation of this mode of formation of carbon-chalcogen bond is shown in equation (1).

R = R¹ = aryl, alkyl

X = Halogen, OTf

EM = SM/ SeM (M = Na, MgBr, Li, SnBu₃)

For example, Singh et al. have demonstrated that, *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine (**1.31**) on reaction with *n*-butyl lithium forms corresponding 2-aryl lithium salt (**1.32**), which reacted with phenyl tellurenyl bromide to give respective monotelluride compound (**1.33**).⁴⁴ On the other hand, 2-aryl lithium salt reacted with tellurium powder to form lithium arenetellurolate (**1.35**), which on further reaction with S/Se powder forms multinuclear chalcogenolates (**1.34**). Lithium arenetellurolate **1.35**, can undergo air oxidation to form ditelluride (**1.36**). The lithium chalcogenolates which can be prepared by the insertion of selenium or tellurium into the C-Li bond, were used to synthesize various chalcogen compounds such as Se/Te, N donor ligands, dichalcogenides, monomeric metal chalcogenolates, and macrocycles (Scheme 1.9).^{15b}

Scheme 1.9: Synthesis of various chalcogen compounds from lithium chalcogenolates

Cohen et al. have reported that magnesium upon ultrasonication with 1,2-dibromoethane in presence of anthracene and further reaction with allyl phenyl sulfide (**1.37**) generates a Grignard-type reagent, allyl magnesium sulfide (**1.38**) *in situ*; which can be captured with electrophiles such as silyl chlorides to form allyl silyl compound (**1.39**).⁴⁵ The conversion of the allylic thioether to the allylmagnesium utilizes a method involving direct reductive magnesiumation in the presence of the magnesium-anthracene complex (Scheme 1.10).

Scheme 1.10: Conversion of the allylic thioether to the allylmagnesium and further reaction

Similarly, Kang et al. have reported a convenient one-pot synthetic method for the formation of alkyl aryl sulfides (**1.43**) from various alkyl halides that have an electron donating or withdrawing group and lithium aryl thiolates (**1.42**) that were prepared *in situ* by direct bromine-lithium exchange.⁴⁶ This method was very quick, catalyst-free, and did not involve use of unstable aryl thiols. It was found that unsaturated alkyl halides gave slightly better yields than did saturated alkyl halides (Scheme 1.11).

Scheme 1.11: Synthesis of alkyl aryl sulfides from lithium aryl thiolates

1.4.2. Transition metal catalyzed/mediated coupling of organohalides with organochalcogens

Transition-metal-catalyzed/mediated coupling reactions involve the cross-coupling of organic halides or hydrocarbons (alkanes or arenes) with REH or R₂E₂ (E = S, Se, Te). Until recently, the efficient and selective construction of C-S bonds in transition-metal-catalyzed transformations remained relatively rare compared to the methods developed for other carbon-heteroatom bonds (C-N, C-O and C-P bonds). Catalyst poisoning by sulfur species, in particular by thiols and disulfides (RSH and R₂S₂), was one of the serious limiting factors in this area. Indeed, it has been reported that even very low concentrations of these sulfur species can rapidly and irreversibly deactivate the catalyst.⁴⁷ This problem has been successfully overcome, and in recent decades, several excellent catalytic systems have been found for C-S bond formation, leading to the development of practical procedures for general synthetic chemistry. Applications were further expanded to include catalytic C-Se bond formation as well as some examples of C-Te bonds.

Scheme 1.12: General mechanistic framework for cross-coupling reaction

Cross-coupling chemistry is a widely recognized approach for the construction of new C-C and C-E (chalcogen) bonds. The general mechanistic framework shown in Scheme 1.12 is well known. Low valent metal complexes were used as catalysts, and the catalytic cycle includes the following stages: (i) oxidative addition of an organic halide R-X, (ii) transmetalation, and (iii) C-heteroatom reductive elimination. Cross-coupling transformations are substitution reactions, and they produce a salt as a byproduct (or HX, which is trapped by a suitable base).^{43a}

Organohalides like alkyl or aryl halides reacted with organochalcogens such as dichalcogenides or thiols in presence of transition metal, ligand and base to form respective monochalcogenides. General pictorial representation of this mode of formation of carbon-chalcogen bond is shown in equation (2).

Scheme 1.13: Pd-catalyzed reaction of aryl halides with thiols

In 1980, Migita et al. reported the first palladium catalyzed reaction of aryl halides with thiols to form monosulfides.⁴⁸ The reaction was useful to prepare symmetrical or unsymmetrical diaryl sulfides and aryl alkyl sulfides (Scheme 1.13). The reaction mechanism does not involve aryl halide radical anions, rather it follows the above mentioned pathway (Scheme 1.12). In the same year, Suzuki et al. have documented the first copper mediated coupling reaction of aryl iodides with thiophenol to form diaryl monosulfides using HMPA as solvent.⁴⁹ Taniguchi et al. have reported nickel-catalyzed alkyl- or arylthiolation of aryl iodide with disulfide to give various aryl monosulfides.⁵⁰ This reaction produces Ni(0) complex from NiBr₂-bpy adduct by the reduction with zinc, and this generated complex works as an activating species to convert aryl iodides into aryl monosulfides under neutral conditions (Scheme 1.14).

Scheme 1.14: Ni-catalyzed reaction of aryl iodides with disulfides

In 2007, Engman and co-workers have reported the synthesis of diaryl monochalcogenides under microwave heating.⁵¹ This was carried out by employing diaryl dichalcogenides and aryl halides as starting materials in the presence of excess magnesium and a catalytic amount of CuI/bipyridyl (Scheme 1.15). The yields of monochalcogenides were significantly

improved under microwave conditions in less reaction times, compared to previous methods.

Scheme 1.15: Cu-catalyzed synthesis of diaryl monochalcogenides

Another important approach to the formation of carbon-chalcogen bond involves the addition reaction of E(chalcogen)-E and E-H bonds to the triple bond of alkynes. The catalytic cycle of these addition reactions includes the following stages: (i) oxidative addition; (ii) alkyne coordination and insertion; and (iii) C-E reductive elimination to form the carbon-heteroatom bond (or protonolysis to form a C-H bond). It should be noted that compared with the cross-coupling reactions discussed above, one important difference in the second stage of the catalytic cycle is that alkyne insertion occurs instead of transmetalation. Such a mechanistic change leads to substantial practical advantages in terms of green chemistry (Scheme 1.16). This is due to the fact that addition reactions are characterized by 100% atom efficiency (no other products like HX, salt, etc.).^{43a}

Scheme 1.16: General mechanistic framework for addition approach

In 2007, Oshima et al. have reported the regio and stereoselective synthesis *Z*-1-phosphino-2-thio-1-alkenes (**1.45**) using addition approach. The hydrothiolation of 1-alkynylphosphines (**1.44**) was catalyzed by Pd(OAc)₂ in EtOH to give corresponding *Z*-1-phosphino-2-thioalkene adducts (Scheme 1.17).⁵² Surprisingly, the addition reaction took

place in an anti-fashion. This probably means that an external nucleophilic attack on the coordinated triple bond is a key step rather than alkyne insertion as observed in the other examples.

Scheme 1.17: Pd-catalyzed hydrothiolation of 1-alkynylphosphines

Vinyl chalcogenides have been prepared using transition metal catalyzed dichalcogenide addition to the double bond of allenes (**1.46**). Ogawa and co-workers reported allene bis-selenation with Ph₂Se₂ and a Pd(PPh₃)₄ catalyst (Scheme 1.18).⁵³ The bis-selenated products (**1.47**) were obtained in good to high yields, but with poor stereo selectivity. Only in the case of cyclohexyl allene, a good yield combined with high selectivity *E/Z* = 93/7 was observed.

Scheme 1.18: Pd-catalyzed allene bis-selenation reaction

Similarly, Taniguchi et al. have reported copper-catalyzed 1,2-hydroxysulfenylation of alkenes (**1.48**), which can be carried out by the use of disulfides and acetic acid under air atmosphere.⁵⁴ This reaction regio- and anti-selectively gave the corresponding 1,2-acetoxysulfides (**1.49**) (Scheme 1.19).

Scheme 1.19: Cu-catalyzed 1,2-hydroxysulfenylation of alkenes

In mechanism, Cu(I)-catalyst acts as a Lewis acid on disulfide or co-oxidant in air to form intermediate (**1.52**). The reaction of this intermediate with styrene gives sulfonium ion (**1.53**) and Cu(I)-thiolate species (**1.50**). Sequentially, 1,2-acetoxysulfide (**1.54**) was obtained in DMF-AcOH. Cu(I)-thiolate species gives disulfide back and Cu(I) species

(**1.51**) under acidic conditions in air, as compound **1.50** cannot carry out sulfenylation of alkene (Scheme 1.20).

Scheme 1.20: Plausible mechanism for Cu-catalyzed 1,2-hydroxysulfonylation

1.4.3. Transition metal catalyzed/mediated C–H bond activation

The capacity to activate ubiquitous, but often inert C–H bonds has far-reaching implications in hydrocarbon functionalization that requires the cleavage of at least one C–H bond. Generally, C–H bonds are difficult to cleave directly due to their thermodynamic stability (calc. 420 kcal mol⁻¹ for primary C–H bonds). Historically, C–C bond formation in alkanes via C–H bond activation usually relied on radical chemistry. The selective functionalization of a C–H bond with a more versatile sulfur group is less common because of the lack of suitable synthetic reagents that can tolerate the presence of sulfur functional groups. To expand this area in synthetic chemistry, the challenge is to identify new transition metal complexes that can overcome the thermodynamic and kinetic barriers to C–H bond activation and perform such difficult transformation with high fidelity.

The utilization of C–H activation through choice of transition metals to form carbon–heteroatom bonds constitutes a powerful tool in pharmaceutical and medicinal chemistry.⁵⁵ The wide range of oxidation states in transition metals accounts for their ability to act as ideal catalysts for C–H activation. During the past decade, numerous critical reviews on transition metal catalyzed formation of C–C bonds *via* C–H activation have appeared in the literature. Despite the promising aspects of C–H activation catalyzed by transition metals, its utility for C–S bond forming reactions became known only until recently.

Arenes undergo C-H activation with transition metal to react with thiols or disulfides to form diaryl monochalcogenides. General pictorial representation of this mode of construction of carbon-chalcogen bond is shown in equation (3).

In 2006, Yu and co-workers demonstrated the cross-coupling of 2-phenylpyridines (**1.55**) with thiophenol or dimethyl disulfide to yield thiolated products (**1.56** and **1.57**) through Cu(OAc)₂-catalyzed C-H activation (Scheme 1.21).⁵⁶ The combined use of the soluble, inexpensive Cu(II) complex as the catalyst and O₂ as a stoichiometric oxidant offered a practical advantage. This reaction tolerates a variety of functional groups (such as alkene, alkoxy, and aldehyde), avoids the use of air-sensitive additives, and overcomes some of the limitations associated with Pd(0)-catalyzed analogues. The authors argued that a single electron transfer (SET) from the aryl ring to the pyridine-coordinated Cu(II) species leading to a cation radical intermediate is the rate-limiting step.

Scheme 1.21: Cu(OAc)₂-catalyzed C-H activation of 2-phenylpyridine

Inamoto et al. have reported the one-pot palladium catalyzed intramolecular cyclization of 1,2,2-triphenyl ethanethiol (**1.58**) into 2,3-diphenyl benzothiophene (**1.59**).⁵⁷ Substituted benzothiophenes were obtained from electronically diverse thioenols in moderate to good yields (Scheme 1.22). Although the detailed mechanism for these reactions remains unclear, this method enables direct C-H functionalization by eliminating the need for an *ortho*-halo substituted precursors.

Scheme 1.22: Pd(II)- catalyzed cyclization of 1,2,2-triphenyl ethanethiol

Cheng and co-workers reported that a combination of CuI (20 mol%) and O₂ catalyzes the direct thiolation of electron-rich arenes (**1.60**) with diphenyl disulfides without the need of any directing groups (Scheme 1.23).⁵⁸ The thiolation reactions carried out at 120 °C in dimethylformamide (DMF) yielded the corresponding monosulfides (**1.61**) in 25–98% yields. The scope of this system seems to be limited to di- and trimethoxy-modified arenes.

Scheme 1.23: CuI-catalyzed direct thiolation of electron-rich arenes

The plausible pathway for the thiolation reaction was outlined in Scheme 1.24. The first step of the mechanism involves the cuprate of the trimethoxybenzene C-H bond to afford ArCu(I) species (**1.62**). In second step, this intermediate reacted with diphenyl disulfide to afford the product and PhSCu(I) (**1.63**). Then, in the next step, intermediate **1.63** reacted with 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene under O₂ to form ArCu(II)SPh intermediate (**1.64**). Finally, the reductive elimination of the Cu(II) complex (**1.64**) affords the product 3a and Cu(0), which is oxidized to Cu(I) by O₂.

Scheme 1.24: Plausible mechanism for direct thiolation

Li et al. have reported the rhodium-catalyzed intermolecular direct C-H thiolation of arenes with aryl and alkyl disulfides for the first time to provide a convenient route to aryl thioethers (**1.65**).⁵⁹ This strategy is compatible with many different directing groups and exhibits excellent functional group tolerance. More significantly, mono- or dithiolation can be selectively achieved, thus providing a straightforward way for selective preparation of aryl thioethers and dithioethers (Scheme 1.25).

Scheme 1.25: Rhodium-catalyzed intermolecular direct C-H thiolation of arenes

1.4.4. Transition metal free direct C-H bond functionalization

The direct C-H functionalization strategy has shortened the synthetic routes to be more efficient in terms of time and resources, and have had an enormous impact. In recent years, much effort has been dedicated towards the development of direct C-H functionalization, which precludes the need for prefunctionalization of both coupling partners and leads to direct C-C bond formation. This kind of oxidative process renders the chemical reactions extremely efficient, in terms of atom economy, time, and ecological resources, and very much in line with the principles of green chemistry.⁶⁰

Recently, transition metal free strategy has emerged as an alternative greener approach for the cross-coupling reactions. The reasons may be summarised in two points. Primarily, most of the transition-metal catalysts are normally very expensive, and the supporting ligands are usually even more expensive and sometimes difficult to prepare. Secondly, most of the transition metals are toxic to different extents, and the removal of trace amounts of transition-metal residues from desired products is quite costly and challenging, while crucial, especially in the pharmaceutical industry.⁶¹

Arenes or alkanes, reacted with thiols or disulfides or aryl sulfonyl chlorides in presence of oxidant or additive to form monosulfides. General pictorial representation of this mode of construction of carbon-chalcogen bond is shown in equation (4).

Scheme 1.26: Sulfenylation of arenes using arylsulfonyl chlorides and PPh₃

For example, You and co-workers developed a one-pot procedure for the sulfenylation of heteroarenes using arylsulfonyl chlorides in combination with triphenylphosphine (Scheme 1.26).⁶² This method represents a highly efficient preparation of diaryl thioethers. It should be emphasized that the protocol for direct arene sulfenylation also works well for heteroarenes such as substituted indolizine and indole substrates.

Scheme 1.27: Probable mechanism for PPh₃ mediated sulfenylation of arenes

A plausible reaction mechanism proposed by the researchers involves the electrophilic attack of arylsulfonyl chloride (ArSCL) by indolizine (**1.66**) at the C3-position to form a di(hetero)aryl sulfide intermediate (**1.67**). The subsequent release of an acidic HCl gas leads to the generation of the corresponding coupling product (**1.68**) (Scheme 1.27).

Scheme 1.28: Direct functionalization of the C(sp³)-H bond of alkanes

Recently, Sun et al. have developed a new protocol for C-S and C-Se bond formation by the direct functionalization of the C(sp³)-H bond of alkanes under metal-free conditions.⁶³ Using ^tBuOO^tBu as the oxidant, the reaction of disulfides or diselenides with alkanes gave

sulfides or selenides in moderate to good yields. The method was very simple and atom economical (Scheme 1.28).

Scheme 1.29: Plausible mechanism for direct C(*sp*³)-H bond functionalization

A plausible reaction mechanism proposed involves homolytic cleavage of DTBP produced *tert*-butoxyl radical. The *tert*-butoxyl radical then abstracted hydrogen from the C-H bond of cyclohexane to afford cyclohexyl radical. Cyclohexyl radical finally reacted with diaryl disulfide to release the product (Scheme 1.29).

1.4.5. Decarboxylative approach

Transition metal-catalyzed decarboxylative cross coupling reactions have emerged as an alternative method to form C-C bonds starting from easily accessible carboxylic acids. These reactions are characterized by the cleavage of C-C bond from carboxylative groups, followed by the formation of new carbon-chalcogen bond at the site where the bond cleavage takes place. Despite its potential utility, early examples of decarboxylative coupling had a limited impact on the synthesis of many types of organic molecules. It was not until the late 2000s that decarboxylative coupling became more prominent, as exemplified by the work of Myers⁶⁴ and Goossen⁶⁵ in the field of metal-catalyzed cross coupling. General pictorial representation of this mode of construction of carbon-chalcogen bond is shown in equation (5).

In contrast with C-H bond activation reactions, decarboxylative cross-coupling reactions through loss of CO₂ generally do not need expensive organometallic reagents, while maintaining the advantage of regioselectivity offered by traditional cross-coupling reactions. In 2009, Duan et al. reported the first direct decarboxylative coupling of *ortho* substituted aryl carboxylic acids (**1.69**) with thiols or disulfides, as an unprecedented synthetic entry to aryl sulfides (**1.70**) (Scheme 1.30).⁶⁶ Importantly, the direct

decarboxylative C–S coupling provides an alternative access to aryl sulfides without the need for halocarbon precursors.

Scheme 1.30: Decarboxylative coupling of *ortho* substituted aryl carboxylic acids

The products were obtained as mixtures of nitrobenzene and aminobenzene sulfides. Critically, primary aliphatic thiols were successfully transformed to aminobenzene sulfides in high yields, while cyclohexanethiol and aromatic thiols yielded nitrobenzene sulfides as major products. Notably, the use of disulfide precursors, which are advantageous over more reactive and odiferous thiols, also afforded the corresponding nitrobenzene sulfides in high yields.⁶⁶

Scheme 1.31: Plausible mechanism for the decarboxylative C–S coupling

The mechanism for the decarboxylative C–S coupling reaction is thought to be initiated by formation of an organometallic nucleophile (**1.72**) upon decarboxylation, followed by the reaction with an electrophilic Pd(II) thiolate intermediate (**1.71**) to form an aryl Pd(II) species (**1.73**) (Scheme 1.31). Subsequent reductive elimination then generates the aryl sulfide coupling product (**1.74**) that can undergo conversion to yield an aminobenzene

sulfide (**1.75**). Oxidation of the reduced Pd(0) species by a Cu(II) catalyst regenerates the Pd(II) compound, thus supporting the continuation of the palladium catalytic cycle.⁶⁶

Despite the success of decarboxylative C–S coupling, these reactions suffer several limitations such as harsh reaction conditions, high temperature, strong bases, and often the need for toxic polar solvents. In addition, an electron-withdrawing group on the arene carboxylic acid is required to afford good yields.

1.5. Conclusions

To further expand the field of carbon-chalcogen bond construction in synthetic chemistry, the challenge for synthetic chemists is to identify sustainable technologies for efficient C–E couplings under mild conditions and to unravel the underlying mechanisms that govern these organic transformations. To this end, we need to develop a range of new approaches that promote green chemistry for both economic and environmental benefits. Previously, there was skepticism on the profitability of sustainable technologies, but a number of examples of pharmaceutical synthesis have shown potential to greatly improve both environmental outcomes and profitability through various modes of innovation.

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CHAPTER 2A

Persulfate Mediated Approach for the Synthesis of Unsymmetrical Diaryl Monochalcogenides

Abstract:

A transition metal free synthetic method has been developed for the synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl chalcogenides (S, Se, and Te) from diaryl dichalcogenides and arenes under oxidative conditions by using potassium persulfate at room temperature. Various substituted arenes such as anisole, thioanisole, diphenyl ether, phenol, naphthol, di- and trimethoxy benzenes, xylene, mesitylene, *N,N*-dimethylaniline, bromo substituted arenes, naphthalene and diaryl dichalcogenides underwent carbon-chalcogen bond forming reaction to give unsymmetrical diaryl chalcogenides in trifluoroacetic acid. For mechanistic understanding of the reaction, a detailed *in-situ* characterization of the intermediates has been carried out by ⁷⁷Se NMR spectroscopy by using diphenyl diselenide as the substrate. ⁷⁷Se NMR study suggests that electrophilic species ArE⁺ is generated by the reaction of diaryl dichalcogenide with persulfate in trifluoroacetic acid. Electrophilic attack of arylchalcogenium ion to the arene may be responsible for the formation of aryl-chalcogen bond.

2a.1. Introduction

The synthesis of aryl C-E (S/Se/Te) bond is one of the fundamental reactions in synthetic chemistry of main group compounds, and represents a key step for the construction of a broad range of organic molecules, which are of paramount importance in drugs, functional materials, and metal complexes.¹⁻³ The carbon-chalcogen coupling reactions were mainly achieved by two pathways: (a) transition metal catalyzed coupling of aryl halides with aryl chalcogenide precursors (Scheme 2a.1)⁴⁻⁷ and (b) conventional methods in which aryllithiums/ aryl Grignards coupled with aryl dichalcogenide precursors.⁸ Synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides from arenes is rarely described in the literature.^{9,10} Recently Copper catalyzed synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides from arenes and diaryl disulfides has been reported using oxygen as an oxidant.⁹ⁱ However, only trimethoxy benzene found to be an efficient substrate for C-S coupling and reaction requires high temperature. Beller et al. have reported a Pd catalyzed synthesis of diaryl sulfides through C-H activation of arenes.^{9j} Nonetheless, arylsulfonyl cyanide (ArSCN) is required as an arylsulfur substrate in this methodology. The corresponding selenium and tellurium analogues of arylsulfonyl cyanides are not easily available.

Scheme 2a.1: Synthesis of Diorganyl chalcogenides

In view of the above mentioned facts, a method which avoids transition metal catalyst, aryl chalcogenyl halides (ArEX), longer reaction time, and high temperature would be highly desirable for the synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides. The synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl selenides by the coupling of phenylselenenyl sulfate (PhSeOSO₃⁻) with arenes under refluxing conditions without using any transition metal catalyst has been reported in 1996 by Engman et al.^{10b} However, synthesis of diaryl sulfide and telluride has not been described. Similarly other methods have also been reported which are limited to the synthesis of diaryl selenides.^{10a,d-f}

We envisioned utilizing diaryl dichalcogenide and arene substrates in the Pd-catalyzed oxidative coupling reaction.¹¹ Diaryl dichalcogenides are readily available substrates and have been used in many transition metal catalyzed coupling reactions.^{5d,6a,7a,d-f,9i} Surprisingly, the reaction also proceeded in the absence of palladium catalyst and presence of potassium persulfate is sufficient for the formation of aryl-sulfur bond. Indeed, slightly better yield of diaryl sulfide was obtained in the absence of palladium catalyst (85% with and 89% without Pd(OAc)₂). In continuation of our work on the synthesis of organochalcogenides and coupling reactions,¹² here, we present a transition metal free methodology for the synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl chalcogenides from arenes and diaryl dichalcogenide substrates at room temperature. By using this alternative chemical reaction, a series of diaryl chalcogenides, particularly electron rich diaryl chalcogenides can be synthesized from diaryl dichalcogenide precursors and arenes in the presence of potassium persulfate without using any transition metal catalyst.

2a.2. Results and discussion

2a.2.1. Optimization of the reaction conditions

Optimization of reaction conditions was carried out using diphenyl disulfide and anisole in the presence of various oxidants in trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (Table 2a.1).

Table 2a.1: Optimization of reaction conditions^a

Entry	Oxidant	Isolated Yield (%)	Entry	Oxidant	Isolated Yield (%)
1	H ₂ O ₂	- ^b	9 ^e	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	85
2	^t BuOOH	20	10 ^f	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	80
3	mCPBA	52	11^d	(NH₄)₂S₂O₈	89
4	AgOAc	- ^b	12 ^d	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₈	74
5	Ag ₂ SO ₄	- ^b	13 ^d	Oxone	45
6	Cu(OAc) ₂	40	14 ^d	PySO ₃	5
7 ^c	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	70	15 ^g	-	- ^b
9	K₂S₂O₈	89	16 ^h	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	- ^b

^a Reaction was carried out at 1 mmol scale using 5 equiv. of anisole, 1 equiv. of diphenyl disulfide, and 2 equiv of oxidant in 5 equiv of TFA, unless otherwise noticed. ^b Product was not observed by TLC. ^{c,d,e,f} 1, 2, 3, and 4 equiv of K₂S₂O₈ were used, respectively. ^g Reaction was carried out in absence of K₂S₂O₈. ^h Instead of TFA, DMF or DMSO were used.

Oxidants such as *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide and *m*-chloroperbenzoic acids were found to be less effective and gave **2a.1** in 20 and 52% yields, respectively and hydrogen peroxide was ineffective (entries 1-3, Table 2a.1). Silver acetate and silver sulfate were found to be inactive for C-S bond formation despite the complete conversion of diaryl disulfide. The use of potassium persulfate ($K_2S_2O_8$) provided a better yield (70-89%) in TFA. We have also screened other sulfur-containing oxidants such as oxone, sodium persulfate, ammonium persulfate and pyridine sulfur trioxide complex. Out of these, the persulfate oxidants resulted in good yields of diaryl sulfide **2a.1** (entries 11-14, Table 2a.1). It was observed that 5 equivalents of TFA are optimum to achieve high yield of diaryl sulfide **2a.1**. Furthermore, presence of TFA seems to be crucial as the reaction failed to yield the corresponding diaryl sulfide in the absence of TFA (entry 16, Table 2a.1).

2a.2.2. Substrate scope of various arenes and diaryl disulfides

After screening various solvents and oxidants, we decided to use $K_2S_2O_8$ as an oxidant and TFA as a solvent to study the scope of this reaction. Under these conditions, a series of arenes were utilized for the synthesis of diaryl monosulfides (**2a.1-2a.28**) and the results are presented in Table 2a.2.

Table 2a.2: Synthesis of diaryl sulfides

Entry	Arene	ArSSAr	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1		2a.1 (89)		
2		2a.2 (45)		
3		2a.3 (73)		
4		2a.4a <i>ortho</i> OH (28) 2a.4b <i>para</i> OH (64)		
5 6		2a.5 R = Me (85) 2a.6 R = ^t Bu (74)		

7		2a.7^b (52)		
8		2a.8 (75)		
9 10 11		2a.9 R = H (92) 2a.10 R = OMe (96) 2a.11 R = Me (94)		
12		2a.12 (55)		
13 14		2a.13 R = H (86) 2a.14 R = OMe (92)		
15 16 17		2a.15 R = H (94) 2a.16 R = Me (75) 2a.17 R = OMe (78)		
18		2a.18 (trace) (30) ^{c,d}		
19		2a.19 (72)		
20		2a.20 (68)		
21		2.21 (76)		
22 23		2a.22 X = CO ₂ H (12) (55) ^c 2a.23 X = NH ₂ (7) (48) ^c		

24		2a.24 (10) (54) ^c		
25		2a.25 (74)		
26		2a.26 (62)		
27		2a.27 (72)		
28		2a.28 (76)		

^a Isolated yield. ^b Structure of **7** was established by 1D-NOE NMR. ^c Reaction was carried out at 80 °C. ^d Formation of 4,4'-methylenebis(*N,N*-dimethylaniline) (50%) was noticed. Structures of diaryl sulfides were established by ¹³C DEPT-135 NMR and by comparing with the reported NMR data.

Arenes with electron donating functional groups such as methoxy, dimethoxy, trimethoxy, methyl thio and alkyl substituents underwent C-S bond formation readily and produced a moderate to good yield of respective diaryl sulfides. Most of the arenes gave monosubstituted arylsulfides; however, 1,2-dimethoxybenzene, *p*-xylene, phenyl ether, and naphthalene underwent double C-S bond formation and produced corresponding bisaryl sulfides exclusively (entries 8, 12, 27 and 28, Table 2a.2). The synthesis of monosubstituted arylsulfides in the above arenes was not successful despite varying the reaction conditions. Arenes with OH functionality such as phenol, substituted phenols, and naphthol also underwent C-S coupling reaction (entries 4-7, 26, Table 2a.2). Synthesis of chalcogen-substituted phenolic compounds is difficult due to the presence of acidic OH proton. Here, a series of phenolic compounds were exploited in arylthiolation reaction, and the desired phenolic sulfides **2a.4a**, **2a.4b**, **2a.5-2a.7** and **2a.26** were obtained in a one-pot reaction.

After studying the hydroxyl-substituted arenes, we turned our attention to amino-substituted arenes. It was observed that aniline was unreactive under optimized reaction conditions. *N,N*-Dimethylaniline underwent coupling reaction sluggishly under heating and yielded the respective diaryl sulfide in poor yield (entry 18, Table 2a.2). Additionally, formation of C-C coupled product, 4,4'-methylenebis(*N,N*-dimethylaniline) was noticed. Arenes with a bromine substituent also underwent C-S bond formation to give desired diaryl sulfides **2a.2**, **2a.7**, and **2a.21**. Next, substituted diaryl disulfides were explored in the coupling reaction for the synthesis of substituted diaryl sulfides (entries 10, 11, 16, 17 and 22-24, Table 2a.2). To our delight, the diaryl disulfides having substituents such as Me, OMe, CO₂H, and NH₂ reacted with arene smoothly and yielded desired sulfides in moderate to excellent yield. Structure of 2-(mesitylthio)benzoic acid **2a.22** was also established by single crystal X-ray crystallography (Figure 2a.1).¹³

Figure 2a.1: X-Ray structure of **2a.22**. Structure shows strong intramolecular S...O interaction. Intramolecular S(1)...O(1) distance (2.747Å) is significantly shorter than the sum of their van der Waals radii (S + O, 3.30 Å).

Similar to substituted aryl disulfides, benzyl disulfide was also exploited for the synthesis of benzyl aryl sulfide **2a.20** under optimized reaction conditions.

Table 2a.3: Synthesis of diaryl selenides/tellurides

Entry	Arene	(ArE) ₂	Product	Isolated Yield (%)
1		2a.29a <i>ortho</i> E = Se (36) 2a.29b <i>para</i> E = Se (49)		
2				2a.30 <i>para</i> E = Te (64)
3		2a.31a <i>ortho</i> (38) 2a.31b <i>para</i> (47)		
4		2a.32 E = Se (92)		
5				2a.33 E = Te (60)
6		2a.34 (93)		
7		2a.35 X = H (95)		
8				2a.36 X = Br (62)
9		2a.37 (94)		
10		2a.38 (55)		
11		2a.39 (57)		
12		2a.40 E = Se (94)		
13				2a.41 E = Te (71)
14		2a.42 (82)		
15		2a.43 (67)		

2a.2.3. Substrate scope of various arenes and diaryl diselenides/ditellurides

The synthesis of diaryl selenides and tellurides was also studied under the optimized reaction conditions (Table 2a.3). Electrophilic selenation in arenes such as phenol, anisole and *N,N*-dimethyl aniline, and thiophene under refluxing conditions has been reported by using phenylselenenyl sulfate.^{10b,c} To check the compatibility of diaryl diselenide in our reaction conditions, various arenes were explored under the optimized reaction conditions. As expected, diaryl and dialkyl diselenides reacted with arenes in a similar fashion as diaryl disulfides and a series of diaryl selenides (**2a.29**, **2a.31**, **2a.32**, **2a.34-2a.40**, **2a.42**, and **2a.43**) were obtained in moderate to excellent (55-95%) yields. Similarly, synthesis of diaryl tellurides **2a.30**, **2a.33**, and **2a.41** was achieved under optimized reaction conditions. However, oxidation of diaryl tellurides (Ar_2Te) into corresponding telluroxides ($\text{Ar}_2\text{Te}=\text{O}$), presumably due to oxidative reaction conditions, was observed during the progress of the reaction. Diaryl telluroxides were readily converted back into diaryl telluride by reducing the reaction mixture with sodium sulfite. Tellurium substituted phenols have attracted considerable interest in biology due to their promising antioxidant function.¹⁴ The introduction of aryltellurium in phenol is challenging. By using this methodology, tellurium-substituted phenolic antioxidants **2a.30** and **2a.41** were obtained in 64% and 71% yield, respectively in one pot.

Scheme 2a.2: Synthesis of selenophene

Carbon-selenium coupling was also applied for the synthesis of selenophene **2a.44** (Scheme 2a.2). Reported synthetic protocols involve 2-iodo-phenethyl-2-bromide substrate and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$,¹⁵ or sodium benzylselenolate ($\text{BenzSe}^+\text{Na}^-$) and butyl ditelluride reagents^{16,2c} for the synthesis of selenophene analogues. Here synthesis of selenophene **2a.44** was achieved in one pot from readily accessible diphenylethyl diselenide **I**, which in turn prepared from diphenylethyl selenide and lithium diselenide.

2a.2.4. Reactivity comparison of diphenyl dichalcogenides

It is worth comparing the reactivity of diphenyl disulfide, diselenide and ditelluride in the persulfate-mediated carbon-chalcogen bond-forming reaction. In a few examples, diphenyl disulfide produced dithiolated products when reacted with arenes (entries 8, 12, 27, and 28,

Table 2a.2) whereas diselenide and ditelluride selectively yielded monoselenated and tellurated compounds, respectively, under similar reaction conditions (Table 2a.3). Diaryl sulfides and selenides were not oxidized into respective sulfoxide and selenoxide under oxidative reaction conditions. On the other hand, diaryl tellurides were completely converted into respective telluroxides. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out reductive workup of the reaction mixture in the case of diaryl telluride synthesis.

2a.3. Mechanistic study

Possible reaction pathway for potassium persulfate mediated synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl chalcogenides is depicted in Scheme 2a.3. It seems that potassium persulfate at first reacts with phenyl dichalcogenide and forms phenylchalcogenium ion intermediates **I** and **II**. Electrophilic addition of phenylchalcogenium ion with the electron rich arene generates the arenium ion intermediate **V**, which may finally give the product diaryl chalcogenide by release of the proton. The presence of potassium persulfate and TFA seems to be crucial for the formation of diaryl chalcogenide in the reaction mixture, as reaction failed to provide monochalcogenide in the absence of both reagents.

Scheme 2a.3: Proposed mechanism for C-E (chalcogen) bond formation

The mechanism of this reaction was also studied by ^{77}Se NMR spectroscopy by taking diphenyl diselenide as a substrate. Electronic nature of ^{77}Se nucleus in the organoselenium compounds can be very well correlated with its NMR chemical shift due to its high sensitivity in NMR. Moreover, based on ^{77}Se NMR study, it is possible to propose the structure of the intermediate involved in the reaction by comparing the ^{77}Se NMR chemical shift value with the related organoselenium compounds (Figure 2a.2). Equimolar reaction

mixture of diphenyl diselenide and potassium persulfate in TFA gave a signal at 788.4 ppm attributed to intermediate **III**. The intermediate **III** has been proposed by Tiecco et al., and also the electrophilic nature of selenium in the intermediate **III** is well illustrated in a series of electrophilic phenylselenation reactions with alkenes.¹⁷ Nonetheless, characterization and electrophilic nature of intermediate **III** have not been studied by ⁷⁷Se NMR.

Figure 2a.2: ⁷⁷Se NMR (CDCl₃) spectra of the proposed intermediate **III**

⁷⁷Se NMR chemical shift values of two selenium species were compared with that of proposed intermediate **III** (Table 2a.4). ⁷⁷Se NMR chemical shift of proposed intermediate **III** was significantly downfield shifted by 327 ppm as compared to diphenyl diselenide (δ 461 ppm) and upfield shifted by 80 ppm as compared to phenylselenenyl bromide, PhSeBr (δ 869 ppm) and the related organoselenenyl bromides (δ 800 \pm 50 ppm).¹⁸ Downfield ⁷⁷Se NMR chemical shift value clearly indicates a significant positive charge on the selenium nucleus, which makes it a better electrophile for the selenation reaction.

Table 2a.4: Comparison of ^{77}Se NMR chemical shift values

Species	^{77}Se NMR chemical shift (ppm)	[III] chemical shift difference
$\text{PhSe}^+ \text{OSO}_3^{2-}$ [III]	788	0
PhSeBr	869	81 (up field)
$\text{Ph}(\text{Se})_2$	461	327 (down field)

A reaction mixture of diphenyl diselenide and potassium persulfate in solvent DMSO- d_6 or CDCl_3 in the absence of TFA yielded no change in the ^{77}Se NMR chemical shift of diphenyl diselenide. Similarly, ^{77}Se NMR chemical shift remains unchanged in the absence of potassium persulfate, which suggests that the presence of TFA and potassium persulfate are crucial for the generation of PhSe^+ from diphenyl diselenide.

To check experimentally whether diaryl dichalcogenide serves as an electrophile in the reaction, phenylselenenyl bromide (PhSeBr) was used as a selenium source that could serve as a better electrophile (scheme 2a.4). Indeed, anisole reacted much faster with phenylselenenyl bromide and gave quantitative yield (94%) of diaryl selenide in 3 h.

Scheme 2a.4: Synthesis of diaryl selenide using phenylselenenyl bromide

^a Observed in the ES-MS spectra. ^b Isolated yield. ^c Relative ratio of **2a.46** and **2a.47** was observed by GC- study.

We also studied the reaction of electron-poor benzonitrile and chlorobenzene with phenylselenenyl bromide in TFA. Benzonitrile reacted sluggishly with phenylselenenyl bromide and expected selenide **2a.45** was not isolated, but its presence was detected by ES-MS. However, the formation of selenanthrene **2a.46** was observed quantitatively in the reaction. Chlorobenzene smoothly reacted with phenylselenenyl bromide and produced *p*-chlorophenyl phenyl selenide **2a.47** in 73% yield along with the cyclized selenanthrene **2a.46** in 27% yield, which was monitored by GC-MS study.

2a.4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have presented a transition metal free method for the synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl sulfides from arenes and readily available diaryl disulfide substrates. Unsymmetrical diaryl sulfides having various functional groups have been synthesized using potassium persulfate in TFA at room temperature. Also, this methodology was successfully extended to the synthesis of diaryl selenides and tellurides. ^{77}Se NMR study of the reaction reveals that it proceeds by the generation of arylchalcogenium ion, which adds to arene leading to the carbon-chalcogen bond formation. This simple transition metal free methodology could be useful for the synthesis of substituted diaryl and arylalkyl chalcogenides from arenes using readily available reagent potassium persulfate.

2a.5. Experimental section

2a.5.1. General experimental details

All NMR experiments were carried out on 400 MHz spectrometer in DMSO- d_6 or CDCl_3 and NMR chemical shifts are reported in ppm referenced to the solvent peaks of CDCl_3 (7.26 ppm for ^1H and 77.16 (± 0.06) ppm for ^{13}C , respectively) or DMSO- d_6 (2.50 ppm for ^1H and 39.50 ppm for ^{13}C , respectively). The ^{77}Se and ^{125}Te NMR spectra were obtained at 76.31 and 126.24 MHz, respectively, in CDCl_3 using diphenyl diselenide and diphenyl ditelluride as external standards. Chemical shifts are reported relative to dimethyl selenide (^{77}Se) and dimethyl telluride (^{125}Te) (0 ppm) by assuming that the resonance of the standards are at 461 and 421 ppm, respectively. High resolution mass spectra (HRMS) are reported for ions of ^{80}Se . Mass analysis is performed on a quadrupole-time of a flight (Q-TOF) mass spectrometer equipped with an ESI source (+ve/-ve) or atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) source. Diphenyl disulfide, 2,2'-dithiodibenzoic acid and diphenyl diselenide were used as received from Aldrich. Substituted aryl disulfides like benzyl disulfide, 4-methylphenyl disulfide, 4-methoxyphenyl disulfide, and 2-aminophenyl disulfide were prepared by the oxidation of respective thiols by using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in the presence of a catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine ditelluride. Silica gel (100-200 mesh size) was used for column chromatography. TLC analysis of reaction mixtures was performed using silica gel plates. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature.

2a.5.2. Experimental procedures and analytical data

General procedure for the synthesis of diaryl chalcogenides

A single-neck round-bottom flask (5 mL) containing TFA (0.4 mL, 4.5 mmol) was charged with anisole (495 mg, 4.5 mmol), diphenyl disulfide (200 mg, 0.9 mmol) and potassium persulfate (495 mg, 1.8 mmol). The resulted reaction mixture was stirred for 16 h at room temperature. For the synthesis of compounds **2a.18** and **2a.22-2a.24**, reaction mixture was heated at 80 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h (**2a.3**, **2a.6-2a.8**, **2a.12**, **2a.13**, **2a.15-2a.17**, **2a.19**, **2a.22**, **2a.24**, **2a.27**, **2a.36**, and **2a.42**), 12 h (**2a.5**, **2a.25**, **2a.26**, **2a.28**, **2a.43**, and **2a.44**), or 16 h (**2a.1**, **2a.2**, **2a.4**, **2a.9-2a.11**, **2a.14**, **2a.18**, **2a.20**, **2a.21**, **2a.23**, **2a.29**, **2a.30-2a.35**, and **2a.37-2a.41**). After completion of the reaction, water (100 mL) was added to the brownish solid and stirred for 30 min. The reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (15 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Crude product was purified by column chromatography using silica gel as stationary phase and hexane as eluent to obtain diaryl sulfide **1** as light yellow oil. Yield (0.35 g, 89%). Compounds with COOH and NH₂ functional groups (**2a.22-2a.24**) are obtained by carrying out aqueous NaHCO₃ work-up, and for tellurides **2a.30**, **2a.33**, and **2a.41**, aqueous NaHSO₃ work-up is carried out.

(4-Methoxyphenyl)(phenyl)sulfane (2a.1). Light yellow oil.^{7a,19} Yield 0.35 g (89%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.48 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.25 (m, 5H), 6.96 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 3.86 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.9, 138.7, 135.4, 131.0, 129.0, 128.3, 125.8, 124.4, 115.1, 55.4. HRMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 216.0628 (calculated for C₁₃H₁₂OS: 216.0609).

(3-Bromo-4-methoxyphenyl)(phenyl)sulfane (2a.2). White solid. Yield 0.12 g (45%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.80 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.65-7.61 (m, 2H), 7.59 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.52-7.46 (m, 3H), 6.96 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 3.92 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 158.2, 145.4, 138.1, 131.2, 130.0, 129.4, 125.9, 124.6, 112.9, 112.2, 56.5. ES-MS ES⁺ *m/z*: 341.0 (calculated for C₁₃H₁₁BrOS + 2Na⁺ - 2H⁺: 341.0).

Methyl(4-(phenylthio)phenyl)sulfane (2a.3). Colorless oil.²⁰ Yield 0.15 g (73%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37-7.31 (m, 6H), 7.28-7.22 (m, 3H), 2.51 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.3, 136.6, 132.4, 130.2, 129.2, 127.2, 126.8, 15.8. HRMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 232.0369 (calculated for C₁₃H₁₂S₂: 232.0375).

2-(Phenylthio)phenol (2a.4a). Light brown oil.²¹ Yield 0.15 g (40%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.56 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.44-7.39 (m, 1H), 7.30-7.23 (m, 2H), 7.22 - 7.15 (m, 1H), 7.14 - 7.08 (m, 3H), 7.02 - 6.96 (m, 1H), 6.55 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.3, 136.9, 135.9, 132.3, 129.2, 126.9, 126.2, 121.3, 116.3, 115.6. HRMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 201.0399 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₀OS - H⁺: 201.0369).

4-(Phenylthio)phenol (2a.4b). Light brown oil.²⁰ Yield 0.14 g (50%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.42-7.37 (dt, *J* = 8.5, 2.1 Hz, 2H), 7.30-7.24 (m, 2H), 7.22-7.15 (m, 3H), 6.88 - 6.84 (dt, *J* = 8.5, 2.0 Hz, 2H), 5.84 - 4.50 (bs, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.0, 138.5, 135.6, 129.0, 128.3, 125.9, 124.5, 116.5. GCMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 202.0 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₀OS - H⁺: 202.0).

4-Methyl-2-(phenylthio)phenol (2a.5). Light yellow oil.²² Yield 0.17 g (85%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.26 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.18-7.12 (m, 2H), 7.11-7.03 (m, 2H), 7.03-6.98 (m, 2H), 6.89 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.27 (s, 1H), 2.20 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.1, 136.9, 136.1, 133.0, 130.6, 129.2, 126.8, 126.0, 115.8, 115.3, 20.3. GCMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 216.0 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₂OS: 216.0).

2-Bromo-4-(phenylthio)phenol (2a.7). Brown oil. Yield: 0.13 g (52%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.61 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.37-7.20 (m, 6H), 7.03 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 5.76 (bs, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.4, 137.2, 136.4, 134.3, 129.2, 129.2, 126.7, 126.5, 116.9, 110.7. HRMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 278.9627 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₉BrOS - H⁺: 278.9474).

(4,5-Dimethoxy-1,2-phenylene)bis(phenylsulfane) (2a.8). White solid.²³ Yield: 0.12 g (75%); mp 94-96 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.33-7.24 (m, 10H), 6.87 (s, 2H), 3.76 (s, 6). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.3, 136.4, 129.9, 129.2, 129.1, 126.7, 116.1, 56.0. HRMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 354.0738 (calculated for C₂₀H₁₇O₂S₂ + H⁺: 354.0743).

Synthesis of *N,N*-dimethyl-4-(phenylthio)aniline (2a.18) and 4,4'-methylenebis(*N,N*-dimethylaniline).

Diphenyl disulfide 200 mg, (0.9 mmol) was added into the flask containing TFA (0.5 mL), potassium persulfate (495 mg, 1.83 mmol) and *N,N*-dimethylaniline (556 mg, 4.58 mmol). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 16 h at 80 °C. After this, reaction mixture was poured into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ethyl acetate (50 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated under *vacuo*. Column chromatography using hexane/

ethyl acetate (9:1) gave two fractions; (i) *N,N*-dimethyl-4-(phenylthio)aniline (**2a.18**). Light green oil.¹⁹ Yield 60 mg (30%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.44-7.40 (m, 2H), 7.25-7.20 (m, 2H), 7.16-7.08 (m, 3H), 6.75 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 3.02 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.9, 140.3, 136.1, 128.7, 126.9, 125.0, 117.5, 113.0, 40.3. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 230.0999 (calculated for C₁₄H₁₅NS + H⁺: 230.0998). (ii) 4,4'-Methylenebis(*N,N*-dimethylaniline). Yellow solid.²⁴ Yield 116 mg (50%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.95 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H), 6.59 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H), 3.70 (s, 2H), 2.79 (s, 12H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.1, 130.4, 129.4, 113.1, 41.0, 39.9. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 255.1846 (calculated for C₁₇H₂₂N₂ + H⁺: 255.1856).

2-(Mesitylthio)benzoic acid (2a.22). Light yellow solid. Yield: 0.1 g (55%); mp 308-310 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.14 (bs, 1H), 7.94 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.29 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.18-7.08 (m, 3H), 6.41 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 2.30 (s, 3H), 2.26 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 167.9, 143.6, 141.9, 139.9, 133.0, 131.8, 130.0, 127.5, 127.3, 124.8, 124.5, 21.5, 21.2. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 295.0775 (calculated for C₁₆H₁₆O₂S + Na: 295.0763).

2-(Mesitylthio)aniline (2a.23). Dark green solid. Yield: 0.19 g (48%); mp 67-69 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.02-6.95 (m, 3H), 6.73 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.61 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz, 2H), 3.70-2.60 (bs, 1H), 2.40 (s, 6H), 2.33 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 143.8, 143.1, 138.8, 129.4, 127.9, 127.5, 126.3, 121.6, 119.8, 115.5, 21.7, 21.1. GCMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 243.1 (calculated for C₁₅H₁₇NS: 243.1).

2-(Phenylselanyl)phenol (2a.29a). Brown oil.²⁵ Yield 60 mg (36%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.68 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.4 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.22-7.30 (m, 5H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 6.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 6.47 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.7, 138.0, 132.3, 130.8, 129.7, 129.5, 126.8, 121.3, 115.2, 114.8. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 248.9816 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₀O⁸⁰Se - H⁺: 248.9813). ⁷⁷Se NMR 247.4 ppm.

4-(Phenylselanyl)phenol (2a.29b). Brown color semi solid.^{7e} Yield 78 mg (49%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.50 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.23-7.30 (m, 3H), 6.82 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 5.41 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.7, 136.7, 133.0, 131.1, 129.3, 126.6, 120.3, 116.7. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 249.9894 (calculated for C₁₂H₁₀O⁸⁰Se: 249.9892). ⁷⁷Se NMR δ 399.4 ppm.

2-(Hexylselanyl)phenol (2a.31a). Yellow color oil. Yield: 60 mg (38%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.58 (dd, $J = 7.7, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.32-7.26 (m, 1H), 7.03 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.85 (dt, $J = 7.4, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.63 (s, 1H), 2.73 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.69-1.58 (m, 2H), 1.43-1.35 (m, 2H), 1.34-1.21 (m, 4H), 0.89 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.7, 137.5, 131.3, 120.8, 115.5, 114.3, 31.2, 30.3, 29.9, 29.3, 22.5, 14.0. HRMS-ES $^+$ m/z : 259.0572 (calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}^{80}\text{Se} + \text{H}^+$: 259.0596). ^{77}Se NMR δ 126.0 ppm.

4-(Hexylselanyl)phenol (2a.31b). Brown oil. Yield: 74 mg (47%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.46-7.41 (m, 2H), 6.79-6.75 (m, 2H), 5.45-4.65 (bs, 1H), 2.83 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.71-1.62 (m, 2H), 1.43-1.36 (m, 2H), 1.31-1.27 (m, 4H), 0.92-0.85 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.1, 135.7, 120.4, 116.2, 31.3, 30.2, 29.7, 29.4, 29.2, 22.5, 14.0. HRMS-ES $^+$ m/z : 257.0448 (calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}^{80}\text{Se} - \text{H}^+$: 257.0439). ^{77}Se NMR δ 281.8 ppm.

(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)(phenyl)selane (2a.34). Light yellow oil.²⁶ Yield: 0.17 g (93%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 (m, 2H), 7.28 (m, 4H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 6.47 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.86 (s, 3H), 3.83 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 161.3, 159.3, 135.3, 132.4, 131.2, 129.2, 126.9, 110.3, 105.7, 99.1, 56.0, 55.5. HRMS-ES $^+$ m/z : 294.0166 (calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2^{80}\text{Se}$: 294.0154). ^{77}Se NMR δ 333.7 ppm.

4-(tert-Butyl)-2-(phenyltellanyl)phenol (2a.41). Brown color semisolid. Yield: 0.18 g (71%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.94 (s, 1H), 7.80 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.44 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.35 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.06 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.82 (s, 1H), 6.72 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.04 (s, 9H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 154.7, 143.1, 140.6, 130.5, 130.2, 130.0, 125.5, 113.8, 112.8, 104.7, 34.1, 31.6. HRMS-APCI $^+$ m/z : 355.0345 (calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}^{129}\text{Te} - \text{H}^+$: 355.0337). ^{125}Te NMR δ 565.0 ppm.

(3-Phenoxyphenyl)(phenyl)selane (2a.42). Colorless oil. Yield: 115 mg (82%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.53 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.49-7.44 (m, 2H), 7.42-7.36 (m, 2H), 7.33-7.26 (m, 3H), 7.17 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.08 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.97 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 157.5, 156.6, 135.7, 132.2, 132.0, 129.9, 129.3, 127.0, 123.8, 123.6, 119.5, 119.3. HRMS-APCI $^+$ m/z : 326.0203 (calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}^{80}\text{Se}$: 326.0205). ^{77}Se NMR δ 404.6 ppm.

Synthesis of 2,3-Dihydrobenzo[b]selenophene (2a.44). A single neck round bottom flask (5 ml) containing TFA (0.6 mL) was charged with diphenylethyl selenide (184 mg, 0.5

mmol) and potassium persulfate (270 mg, 1.0 mmol). The resultant reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h at room temperature. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was poured into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ethyl acetate (50 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated under *vacuo*. Column chromatography using hexane gave 2,3-dihydrobenzo[b]selenophene (**2a.44**). Yellow oil.¹⁵ Yield 80 mg (40%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.33-7.31(m, 1H), 7.17-7.15 (m, 1H), 7.09-7.03 (m, 2H), 3.37 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 143.2, 137.0, 127.3, 125.7, 124.8, 124.7, 38.7, 26.6. HRMS-ES⁺*m/z*: 183.9751 (calculated for C₈H₈⁸⁰Se: 183.9786).

Synthesis of (4-methoxyphenyl)(phenyl)selane (2a.32) using PhSeBr. Phenylselenenyl bromide (236 mg, 1.0 mmol) was added into a flask containing TFA (0.5 mL), potassium persulfate 270 mg (1.0 mmol) and anisole 540 mg (5.0 mmol). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. Then, reaction mixture was poured into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ethyl acetate (50 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under *vacuo*. Column chromatography using hexane gave (4-Methoxyphenyl)(phenyl)selane **2a.32**. Colorless oil.^{7f} Yield: 0.25 g (94%);

Selenanthrene (2a.46) and (4-Chlorophenyl)(phenyl)selane (2a.47). Phenylselenenyl bromide 236 mg, (1.0 mmol) was added into a flask containing TFA (0.5 mL), potassium persulfate 270 mg (1.0 mmol) and chlorobenzene (563 mg, 5.0 mmol). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. Then, the reaction mixture was poured into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ethyl acetate (50 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under *vacuo*. Column chromatography using hexane gave mixture of (4-chlorophenyl)(phenyl)selane **2a.47** and selenanthrene **2a.46**. GC-MS study shows 73% of **2a.47** and 27% of **2a.46** in the mixture. Analytical data of **2a.47** and **2a.46**; Yellow solid.²⁷ Yield 0.41 g; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.45-7.41 (m), 7.40-7.35 (m), 7.30-7.27 (m), 7.25-7.22 (m). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, CDCl₃) δ 135.5, 134.4, 133.4, 132.6, 132.3, 129.7, 129.5, 122.4. GC-MS for **2a.47**: retention time = 9.1 min, *m/z*: 267.9 (calculated for C₁₂H₉Cl⁸⁰Se: 267.9); GC-MS for **2a.46**: retention time = 9.8 min, *m/z*: 311.8 (calculated for C₁₂H₈⁸⁰Se₂: 311.8). ⁷⁷Se NMR δ 473.6, 412.6.

Synthesis of Selenanthrene (2a.46). Phenylselenenyl bromide (236 mg, 1.0 mmol) was added into a flask containing TFA (0.5 mL), potassium persulfate (270 mg, 1.0 mmol) and benzonitrile (515 mg, 5.0 mmol). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h, poured

into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ethyl acetate (50 mL x 3), dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated under *vacuo*. Column chromatography using hexane gave selenanthrene **2a.46**. Yellow solid.²⁸ Yield: 0.13 g (84%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.45-7.41 (m, 4H), 7.39-7.35 (m, 4H); ¹³C NMR (100MHz, CDCl₃) δ 133.4, 132.3, 129.5, 122.4. GCMS-ES⁺ *m/z*: 311.8 (calculated for C₁₂H₈⁸⁰Se₂: 311.8). ⁷⁷Se NMR δ 473.7 ppm.

Synthesis and *in situ* characterization of reaction intermediates by ⁷⁷Se NMR.

In a single necked flask (5 mL) containing TFA (0.3 mL) were added diphenyl diselenide (50 mg, 0.16 mmol) and potassium persulfate (43 mg, 0.16 mmol) and the resulted reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. After this, 0.1 mL of the reaction mixture was transferred to NMR tube containing 0.6 mL of CDCl₃. ⁷⁷Se NMR was recorded for 12 h and 2000 scans were made in -200 to 600 ppm range and 600 to 1400 ppm range. A peak at 788 ppm presumably due to intermediate **III** was observed. To understand the effect of TFA on chemical shift, the ⁷⁷Se NMR experiment was also carried out on diphenyl diselenide in TFA using CDCl₃, without adding potassium persulfate. A peak at 460 ppm was observed that corresponds to diphenyl diselenide (461 ppm).

Table 2a.5: The crystallographic details of compound **2a.22**

Compound	2a.22
Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ S
Molecular weight	272.35
CCDC number	897377
<i>a</i>(Å), <i>b</i>(Å), <i>c</i>(Å), <i>V</i>(Å³)	7.6506(8), 8.0881(9), 11.7507(13), 693.42(13)
<i>α</i>, <i>β</i>, <i>γ</i> (°)	83.871(6), 84.899(6), 73.945(6)
Crystal System	Triclinic
Space Group	P-1
T (K)	130(2) K
Z	2
<i>ρ</i> (g/cm³)	1.304
<i>μ</i> (mm⁻¹)	0.228
F (000)	288
<i>θ</i> min, max (°)	1.75, 28.91
<i>h</i>; <i>k</i>; <i>l</i> (min, max)	-9, 10; -10, 10; -15, 14
No. of reflections	12588
No. of parameters	179
R₁ all, R₁ obs	0.0580, 0.0487
wR₂ all, wR₂ obs	0.1754, 0.1585
G. F.	1.311

2a.6. Representative NMR spectra of diaryl monochalcogenides

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.1

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.2

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.4a

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.4b

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.7

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.22

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.28

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.31a

^{13}C -DEPT and ^{77}Se NMR spectra of the compound 2a.31a

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.31b

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2a.42

1D NOE-NMR spectrum of 2a.7 in CDCl₃ : (a comparison with ¹H NMR); Hydrogen OH (5.67 ppm) irradiated in this experiment

⁷⁷Se NMR spectrum of intermediate **III** in CDCl₃

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CHAPTER 2B

Persulfate Mediated Approach for the Sulfenylation and Bis-sulfenylation of Indoles

Abstract:

A practical method which avoids metal and halogen for the synthesis of 3-aryltioindoles from indoles and diaryl disulfides using ammonium persulfate in methanol has been presented. This method is compatible with functionalities having active hydrogen groups such as hydroxyl, amino and acid groups. Moreover, both *N*-protected and *N*-H free indoles were compatible in this reaction system and it exhibited wide scope with respect to different indoles and diaryl disulfides. Furthermore, a double C-H sulfenylation of indoles at 2 and 3-positions has also been achieved by the addition of stoichiometric amount of iodine.

2b.1. Introduction

Thiolated indole moieties are an important class of organo-sulfur heterocyclic compounds having greater therapeutic value in treatment of HIV, cancer, cardiovascular, and bacterial diseases.^{1,2} Among the various indole derivatives known, 3-arylthioindoles have attracted considerable interest (Chart 2b.1). For example, compound **A** exhibit strong antitumor activity, while compounds **B** and **C** are useful for the treatment of affective, respiratory disorders respectively.^{1h}

Chart 2b.1. Biologically important 3-arylthioindoles

As a result, two synthetic routes have been developed to construct thiolated indoles. One route involves the introduction of substituents by direct sulfenylation of an existing indole ring,³⁻¹³ whereas the other route involves the cyclization reactions of 2-alkynylanilines¹⁴ or *N,N*-dialkyl-2-iodoanilines.¹⁵ Most of the methodologies derived from the first synthetic route involve the usage of high boiling solvents such as DMSO³ and DMF,⁴ strong base,⁵ and presence of transition metal catalysts⁶ or halogenating reagents *N*-bromo-succinimide^{4b} and trichloroisocyanuric acid^{6e} to accomplish sulfenylation in indoles using arylsulfenyl halides,⁷ aryl/ alkyl thiols,^{5a,6a,b,8} aryl disulfides,^{3,4c,6c,9} aryl-*N*-thioimides,¹⁰ arylsulfonium salts,¹¹ and sulfonyl hydrazides¹² as a source of organosulfur moiety. Most of the sulfur sources are either difficult to prepare or air, moisture sensitive and expensive.

The development of a methodology which involves mild reaction conditions, readily available reagents and substrates will be highly desirable for the synthesis of sulfenyl indoles. Mild reaction conditions enable installation of wide range of functional groups such as ether, bromide, and most importantly functionalities having acidic protons such as hydroxyl, amine, and carboxylic acid which could be helpful in late stage transformation/functionalization for the synthesis of substituted sulfenyl indoles. Although, many methods have been developed to construct sulfenyl indoles, synthesis of arylthiolated indoles having acidic proton functional groups (OH, NH₂, CO₂H etc) has not been well documented to date.

Also a methodology which can cause double C-H sulfenylation in indoles will be interesting because the double C-H sulfenylation in indoles remained elusive. Recently, our group has launched a program to synthesize organo ethers, sulfur, selenium and tellurium compounds by using new benign reaction conditions and reagents.¹⁶ Here, in continuation of our work on organochalcogen chemistry, we present an economical and mild methodology for the regioselective synthesis of diversely substituted 3-sulfenyl indoles. Moreover, double C-H thiolation in indoles has been accomplished to give 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indoles.

2b.2. Results and discussion

2b.2.1. Screening of the reaction conditions

Phenyl disulfide and indole were chosen as substrates in the presence of various oxidants such as hydrogen peroxide, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide, potassium, and ammonium persulfates in methanol at reflux temperature to screen for the optimal reaction conditions (entries 1-5, Table 2b.1). Among these, ammonium persulfate (2 equiv) gave good yield of the sulfenylated product **2b.1**. Increasing or decreasing of oxidant loading resulted in a poor yield of **2b.1**. A number of solvents like THF, Dichloromethane, CH₃CN, DMF, and DMSO were examined; nonetheless, better yield could not be obtained (entries 6-10, Table 2b.1).

Table 2b.1: Screening of reaction conditions^a

Entry	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Entry	Solvent ^b	Yield (%)
1	H ₂ O ₂	20	6	THF	22
2	<i>t</i> BuOOH	25	7	CH ₂ Cl ₂	35
3	Oxone	47	8	CH ₃ CN	43
4	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	61	9	DMF	trace
5	(NH ₄) ₂ S ₂ O ₈	68	10	DMSO	trace

^a The reaction was carried out on a 1 mmol scale using 2 equiv. of indole, 1 equiv. of phenyl disulfide, and 2 equiv. of oxidant in 5 mL of CH₃OH at reflux (70 °C) temperature, unless otherwise noted. ^b 5 mL of solvent is used instead of CH₃OH.

2b.2.2. Substrate scope of various indoles and diaryl disulfides

With the optimized reaction conditions in hand, a variety of indoles and aryl disulfides were tested to determine the scope and limitations of this method. Results presented in Scheme 2b.1 demonstrate that a series of aryl disulfides underwent smooth transformations to give the structurally diverse sulfenyl indoles **2b.1-2b.19** in 46-94% yields.

At first, we examined the reaction of indole with substituted aryl disulfides. Disulfides having electron donating groups like *p*-methyl, *p*-methoxy, *o*-amino and *p*-hydroxy gave the respective sulfenylated products (**2b.2-2b.5**) with indole in good yields. Carboxylic acid containing aryl disulfide also underwent this reaction smoothly with indole resulting 46% yield of **2b.6**. Synthesis of hydroxy substituted 3-arylthio indoles has not been explored to date, whereas amino and acid substituted 3-arylthioindoles are scarcely found in the literature.^{13k,17} The present mild methodology gives an access to a series of hydroxyl, amino, acid substituted sulfenyl indoles **2b.4-2b.6**, **2b.9** and **2b.16-2b.18**. Phenyl diselenide also reacted with indole under optimized reaction conditions in methanol to produce 3-selenylated indole **2b.7** in 80% yield.

Next, the sulfenylation reaction of diaryl disulfides with variously substituted indoles was explored. The electronic properties of the groups attached to the indole have little effect on the outcome of the reaction as the yields of the sulfenyl indoles **2b.8-2b.19** remained nearly the same. Indoles with electron donating methoxy group and electron withdrawing 5-nitro and 5-bromo groups reacted with diaryl disulfides to give the sulfenyl indoles **2b.8-2b.13** in 52-94% yields. The structure of synthesized 5-nitro-3-(*p*-tolylthio)-1*H*-indole **2b.11** was also established by an X-ray single crystal structure study (Figure 2b.1).

Figure 2b.1: X-Ray crystal structure of **2b.11**

Scheme 2b.1: Synthesis of monosulfenyl indoles^a

^a The reaction was carried out on a 1 mmol scale using 2 equiv. of indole, 1 equiv. of phenyl disulfide, and 2 equiv. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ in 5 mL of CH_3OH at reflux (70 °C) temperature.

Similarly, the sulfenylation reaction of substituted indoles with substituted disulfides was tested. *N*-Methyl indole reacted with *p*-methoxy, *p*-hydroxy, and *o*-aminophenyl disulfides to afford the sulfenyl indoles **2b.14-2b.17** in 70-84% yields. 2-Methyl indole also reacted smoothly with *p*-methoxy and *o*-aminophenyl disulfides resulting in the respective products **2b.18** and **2b.19** in 72 and 79% yields, respectively.

2b.2.3. Bis-sulfenylation of indoles

Assuming that 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indoles could be generated by a persulfate mediated reaction in methanol, we have conducted a model reaction with 1 mmol of phenyl disulfide, 1 mmol of indole and 2 mmol ammonium persulfate under optimized reaction conditions. Unfortunately, varying the equiv. of persulfate and/or disulfide did not provide any 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole. Interestingly, addition of iodine to the reaction mixture provided 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.20**. Varying the loading of iodine has yielded the mixture of mono and disulfenyl indoles and one equiv. of iodine was noticed to be optimum for maximum yield (44%) of 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.20** (Table 2b.2).

Table 2b.2: 2,3-bis sulfenylation of indoles^a

Entry	Indole	ArSSAr	Product	Yield (%)
1		2b.20 X = H (44)		
2		2b.21 X = OCH ₃ (62)		
3		2b.22 (71)		

^a The reaction was carried out on a 1 mmol scale using 1 equiv. of indole, 1 equiv. of phenyl disulfide, 1 equiv. of iodine and 2 equiv. of (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ in 5 mL of CH₃OH at reflux (70 °C) temperature.

Previously, the synthesis of 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indoles had been achieved by Hamel et al.^{13g,h} utilizing aryl sulfenyl chlorides as sulfur source. To the best of our knowledge, there are no reports in the literature on accomplishing the synthesis of 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indoles under mild reaction conditions and using readily available sulfur precursors. Herein, we have reported the synthesis of 2,3-bis sulfenyl indoles exploiting diaryl disulfide substrates. Phenyl disulfide and *p*-methoxyphenyl disulfide reacted smoothly under the optimized reaction conditions to give the respective 2,3-bis sulfenyl indoles **2b.20** and **2b.21** in moderate yields (Table 2b.2, entries 1 and 2). 2,3-Bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.21** was also characterized by single a single X-ray crystal structure study (Figure 2b.2).

Figure 2b.2: X-Ray crystal structure of **2b.21**

We have also attempted the bis-sulfenylation reaction in *N*-methyl indole. *p*-Methoxy disulfide reacted with *N*-methyl indole in methanol and gave the respective 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.22** in 71% yield (Table 2b.2, entry 3). Based on the above experimental results and persulfate mediated reactions^{16e,18,19} a possible mechanism has been depicted in Scheme 2b.2.

2b.2.4. Proposed reaction mechanism

First, ammonium persulfate reacts with diaryl disulfide to form aryl sulfenium ion intermediates **I** and **II**. The electrophilic aryl sulfenium ion could add on to the indole moiety to produce indole intermediate **III**, which may undergo deprotonation to give the desired monosulfenyl indole **2b.1**.

Scheme 2b.2: Proposed mechanism for 3- and 2,3-bis arylthiolation in indole

For the formation of 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.20**, the presence of iodine and persulfate is crucial in the reaction as iodine or persulfate alone is noticed to be ineffective for 2,3 C-H sulfenylation of indole. The formation of 2,3-bis thiolated product in the presence of iodine can be speculated by proposing a less hindered iodophenylthiolate intermediate, which may attack on the third position leading to 3,3-bis-substituted indolenium intermediate **IV**.^{3c,6c,13h,m} Positive charge on nitrogen could enforce one of the phenylthio groups from position 3 to 2 forming an episulfonium species **V** and subsequent release of proton can give 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole **2b.20**.

2b.3. Conclusions

In summary, a metal and halogen free, simple and mild method for the selective sulfenylation of indoles has been developed in methanol. The present methodology is not moisture sensitive and is carried out in low boiling solvent methanol. In addition, both *N*-protected and unprotected indoles and disulfides with acidic protons such as amino, hydroxyl, acid groups can be tolerated well in this methodology. Moreover, the methodology can be extended to synthesize 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indoles with the addition of stoichiometric amount of iodine, making use of diaryl disulfides as the sulfur source.

2b.4. Experimental section

2b.4.1. General experimental details

All NMR experiments were carried out on 400 MHz spectrometer in DMSO or CDCl₃ and NMR chemical shifts are reported in ppm referenced to the solvent peaks of CDCl₃ (7.26 ppm for ¹H and 77.16 (± 0.06) ppm for ¹³C, respectively) or DMSO (2.50 ppm for ¹H and 39.50 ppm for ¹³C, respectively). Mass analysis is performed on quadrupole-time of flight (Q-TOF) mass spectrometer equipped with an ESI source (+ve/-ve). Phenyl disulfide, 2,2'-dithiodibenzoic acid, and phenyl diselenide were used as received from Sigma-Aldrich. Substituted aryl disulfides like 4-methylphenyl disulfide, 4-methoxyphenyl disulfide, and 2-aminophenyl disulfide were prepared by the oxidation of respective thiols by using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in the presence of catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine ditelluride. Silica gel (100-200 mesh size) was used for column chromatography. TLC analysis of reaction mixtures was performed using silica gel plates.

2b.4.2. Synthetic procedures and analytical data

2b.4.2.1. Synthetic procedure for 3-sulfenylation of indoles

Methanol (5 mL) was added to a single neck flask (10 mL) containing stirrer bar. To this flask, diphenyl disulfide (218 mg, 1.0 mmol) and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ (456 mg, 2.0 mmol) were added and stirred at reflux temperature (70 °C) for 3 hours. Then, reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, indole (234 mg, 2.0 mmol) was added and resultant reaction mixture was again refluxed at 70 °C for 3-4 hours. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (10-20% EA: 90-80% hexane). Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured into water, and extracted four times with 20 mL of ethyl acetate. The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, and filtered. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified by column chromatography (eluent: hexane/ethyl acetate) to yield sulfenylated indole as product.

3-(Phenylthio)-1*H*-indole (2b.1).²⁰

White solid. Yield 0.31 g (68%); mp 147-149 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.29 (bs, 1H), 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.21-7.17 (m, 1H), 7.11-7.01 (m, 5H), 7.00-6.94 (m, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.2, 136.5, 130.7, 129.1, 128.7, 125.9, 124.8, 123.1, 120.9, 119.7, 111.6, 102.9; GCMS-EI: retention time = 10.2 min, *m/z* = 225.0.

3-(*p*-Tolylthio)-1*H*-indole (2b.2).²¹

Brown solid. Yield 0.36 g (76%); mp 122-125 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.34 (bs, 1H), 7.62 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.46-7.39 (m, 2H), 7.28-7.22 (m, 1H), 7.18-7.12 (m, 1H), 7.06-6.95 (m, 4H), 2.25 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100MHz,CDCl₃) δ 136.5, 135.5, 134.7, 130.5, 129.5, 129.1, 126.3, 123.0, 120.9, 119.7, 111.6, 103.5, 20.9;GCMS-EI: retention time = 10.2 min, *m/z* = 239.0.

3-((4-Methoxyphenyl)thio)-1*H*-indole (2b.3).²²

Pale yellow solid. Yield 0.40 g (78%); mp 120-123 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.33 (bs, 1H), 7.62 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.46-7.38 (m, 2H), 7.26-7.21 (m, 1H), 7.17-7.09 (m, 3H), 6.72 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 3.72 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.8, 136.5, 130.0, 129.5, 129.0, 128.6, 122.9, 120.8, 119.7, 114.5, 111.5, 104.7, 55.3. GCMS-EI: retention time = 11.2 min, *m/z* = 254.9.

4-((1*H*-indol-3-yl)thio)phenol (2b.4).

Light green solid. Yield 0.31 g (64%); mp 169-172 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 11.50 (s, 1H), 9.31 (s, 1H), 7.65 (d, *J* = 2.5 Hz, 1H), 7.41 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.04-6.95 (m, 3H), 6.61 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 156.1, 137.0, 131.9, 129.4, 129.1, 127.4, 122.4, 120.3, 118.9, 116.4, 112.6, 102.6. HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 240.0495 (Calculated for C₁₄H₁₁NOS - H⁺: 240.0478).

2-((1*H*-indol-3-yl)thio)aniline (2b.5).

Yellow solid. Yield 0.28 g (58%); mp 89-92 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.35 (bs, 1H), 7.66 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.33-7.28 (m, 2H), 7.25-7.11 (m, 3H), 7.01 (dt, *J* = 7.6, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 6.67 (dt, *J* = 8.0, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 6.61 (dt, *J* = 7.5, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 4.19 (bs, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 145.6, 136.4, 131.9, 129.2, 128.8, 128.1, 122.9, 120.9, 120.7, 119.4, 119.0, 115.4, 111.6, 104.1. GCMS-EI: retention time = 11.8 min, *m/z* = 239.9.

2-((1*H*-indol-3-yl)thio)benzoic acid (2b.6).

Green solid. Yield 0.25 g (46%); mp 242-246 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.05 (bs, 1H), 11.69 (s, 1H), 7.89 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.70 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.29 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.20-7.13 (m, 2H), 7.10-6.99 (m, 2H), 6.66 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 167.9, 144.2, 137.4, 133.1, 132.5, 131.4, 129.2, 127.1, 126.1, 124.2, 122.6, 120.6, 118.8, 112.9, 100.5. HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 270.0560 (Calculated for C₁₅H₁₁NO₂S + H⁺: 270.0583).

3-(Phenylselanyl)-1H-indole (2b.7).

White solid. Yield 0.44 g (80%); mp 135-138 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.39 (bs, 1H), 7.64 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.46 (d, *J* = 2.5 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.29-7.21 (m, 3H), 7.20-7.06 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, CDCl₃) δ 136.4, 133.8, 131.2, 130.0, 129.0, 128.7, 125.6, 123.0, 120.9, 120.4, 111.4, 98.2. GCMS-EI: retention time = 9.9 min, *m/z* = 272.9.

2b.4.2.2. Synthetic procedure for 2,3-bis-sulfenylation of indoles:

Methanol (5 mL) was added to a single neck flask (10 mL) containing stirrer bar. To this flask, diphenyl disulfide (218 mg, 1.0 mmol) and indole (117 mg, 1.0 mmol) were added. Then, (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ (456 mg, 2.0 mmol) and I₂ (254 mg, 1.0 mmol) were added portion wise in sequence and resultant reaction mixture was refluxed at 70 °C for 6-7 hours. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (10-20% EA: 90-80% hexane). Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured into water, and extracted four times with 20 mL of ethyl acetate. The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, and filtered. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified by column chromatography (eluent: hexane/ethyl acetate) to yield 2,3-bis-sulfenyl indole as product.

2,3-Bis(phenylthio)-1H-indole (2b.20).²⁰

Pale yellow solid. Yield 0.15 g (44%); mp 96-98 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.34 (bs, 1H), 7.58 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.31 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.28-7.19 (m, 6H), 7.17-7.09 (m, 5H), 7.08-7.03 (m, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.1, 136.9, 134.3, 133.6, 130.0, 129.8, 129.4, 128.7, 127.3, 126.6, 125.1, 123.9, 121.4, 119.9, 111.1, 109.2. LRMS-ESI *m/z*: 333.0629 (Calculated for C₂₀H₁₅NS₂ : 333.0646).

2,3-Bis((4-methoxyphenyl)thio)-1H-indole (2b.21).^{13g}

Brown solid. Yield 0.24 g (62%); mp 134-137 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.10 (bs, 1H), 7.57 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.23 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.20-7.08 (m, 4H), 6.82 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.71 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.72 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.9, 157.9, 136.5, 135.6, 133.7, 130.3, 129.3, 128.7, 127.2, 123.3, 123.2, 121.0, 119.5, 115.2, 114.5, 110.8, 55.4, 55.3. LRMS-ESI *m/z*: 393.0655 (Calculated for C₂₂H₁₉NO₂S₂ : 393.0857).

2,3-Bis((4-methoxyphenyl)thio)-1-methyl-1H-indole (2b.22).

Gray solid. Yield 0.29 g (71%); mp 92-94 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.68 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.36-7.26 (m, 2H), 7.19-7.04 (m, 5H), 6.70 (t, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 4H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.72 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 158.7, 158.0, 138.2, 135.4, 130.5, 129.5, 129.2, 129.1, 126.1, 123.7, 120.9, 120.3, 114.9, 114.4, 112.0, 110.1, 55.33, 55.30, 31.1. LRMS-ESI *m/z*: 408.1116 (Calculated for C₂₃H₂₁NO₂S₂ + H⁺: 408.1087).

Table 2b.3: The crystallographic details of compounds **2b.11** and **2b.21**

Compound	2b.11	2b.21
Molecular formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂
Molecular weight	272.33	419.52
CCDC number	953902	952234
<i>a</i>(Å), <i>b</i>(Å), <i>c</i>(Å), <i>V</i>(Å³)	20.173(6), 51.635(14), 5.5236(15), 5754(3)	7.5669(4), 10.6356(5), 24.4275(12), 1949.76(17)
<i>α</i>, <i>β</i>, <i>γ</i> (°)	90, 90, 90	90, 97.345(2), 90
Crystal System	Orthorhombic	Monoclinic
Space Group	Fdd2	P 2 ₁ /n
T (K)	120(2) K	296(2) K
Z	16	4
ρ (g/cm³)	1.258	1.429
μ (mm⁻¹)	0.224	0.296
F (000)	2274	876
θ min, max (°)	2.56, 27.74	2.55, 26.37
h; k; l (min, max)	-26, 26; -66, 66; -5, 7	-8, 9; -13, 13; -30, 30
No. of reflections	23149	3878
No. of parameters	183	246
R₁ all, R₁ obs	0.2406, 0.0752	0.0585, 0.0419
wR₂ all, wR₂ obs	0.2192, 0.1652	0.1476, 0.1347
G. F.	1.012	1.102

2b.5. Representative NMR spectra of 3-sulfenyl indoles

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2b.2

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2b.4 (in DMSO- d_6)

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2b.5

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 2b.7

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound 2b.20

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CHAPTER 3

Silver Acetate Mediated Thio-Acetoxylation and TFA Triggered Cyclization of Amino Disulfides with Unactivated Alkenes: Synthesis of 3-Aryl/Alkyl-1,4-benzothiazines

Abstract:

A convenient strategy for the synthesis of 3-aryl/alkyl-1,4-benzothiazines has been developed. This reaction proceeds via 1,2-thioacetoxylation of an alkene with silver acetate and acetic acid as an additive followed by cyclization using TFA. The addition of alkene took place in a regioselective manner, forming exclusively one regioisomer, which also confirmed by X-ray crystal study. Various differently substituted alkenes such as aromatic and aliphatic olefins, were coupled with amino disulfides to form a library of benzothiazine derivatives.

3.1. Introduction

Organic molecules containing C-S bonds widely exist in many biologically active compounds.¹ They are also frequently used as building blocks of many drugs, functional materials and metal complexes.² Although the methods for C-N³ and C-O⁴ bond formation receive extensive attention in the field of traditional metal-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions, the efficient construction of a C-S bond through transition-metal catalysis still needs more studies. Recently, progress has been made in C-S cross-coupling reactions catalyzed by Pd,⁵ Cu,⁶ and Ni,⁷ but many of these methods depend on harsh reaction conditions such as high reaction temperature, the necessity of strong base, and use of expensive ligands, and they suffer from limited substrate scope. Very recently, silver mediated C-S coupling reactions were realized with ketene ainals,^{8a,b} enamides,^{8c} and in a decarboxylative manner with aliphatic carboxylic acids.^{8d} Consequently, it remains important to explore new approaches for the efficient construction of C-S bonds.

Phenothiazines are prevalent motifs in various anti-psychotic and anti-histaminic drugs.⁹ These also acts as norA pump inhibitors. In particular, 3-phenyl-1,4-benzothiazine derivatives, designed by the structural minimization of phenothiazines, show modest or no intrinsic antistaphylococcal activity and restore the antibacterial activity of CPX against norA-overexpressing *Staphylococcus aureus* strains.¹⁰ Furthermore, these compounds were proved to be useful in the treatment and/or prevention of various disorders such as arteriosclerosis, cardiac arrhythmias, inflammatory and immunological diseases (Figure 3.1).¹¹ Despite the diverse biological activities of the benzothiazine derivatives, the synthesis of these compounds has rarely been documented in the literature.¹²

Figure 3.1: Bioactive 3-phenyl-1,4-benzothiazine derivatives

Benzothiazines can be prepared either by the reaction of corresponding 2-aminothiophenol/its sodium salt with a substituted α -bromo acetophenone (eqn (1), Scheme 3.1)¹¹ or by the reaction of benzene sulfonyl chlorides with substituted acetophenones to

obtain 2-(2-phenylthio)-1-phenylethanones, which then can be reduced with LiAlH₄ to afford, after spontaneous cyclization, the benzothiazines (eqn (2), Scheme 3.1).^{12b}

Moreover, transition metal catalyzed/mediated simultaneous C-S and C-N coupling in an intermolecular fashion is difficult and has not been addressed, particularly the addition of S and N atoms to a C=C bond. Based on our interest in synthesizing phenothiazine derivatives, herein we report a silver-mediated synthesis of 3-phenyl-1,4-benzothiazines from unactivated alkenes, which include enough complexity, substrate scope and avoid the use pre-functionalized substrates such as sulfenyl chlorides and halogenated substrates.

Scheme 3.1: Approaches for 3-phenyl-1,4-benzothiazine derivatives

3.2. Results and discussion

3.2.1. Variation of reaction parameters

We envisioned that the reaction of 2-acetylaminophenyl disulfide with 4-methyl styrene, using Pd(OAc)₂ and AgOAc as an additive, under acidic conditions would result in benzothiazine derivative **3.2a** via C-N and C-S coupling cascade. Unfortunately, we obtained only the thio-acetoxyated product **3.1a**, in 90% yield. However, when a control reaction was performed with AgOAc alone under acidic conditions, it resulted in product **3.1a** in 72% yield (entry 1, Table 3.1). Interestingly, the addition of 0.5 mL TFA to the thio-acetoxyated compound **3.1a**, resulted in intramolecular dehydroacetoxylation at both carbon and nitrogen ends, resulting in 3-tolyl-1,4-benzothiazine (**3.2a**) in 63% yield.

Encouraged by this result, we varied different parameters for the reaction (Table 3.1). Various silver salts such as AgNO₃, AgTFA, AgOTf, Ag₂CO₃ and solvents like toluene, MeCN, DMSO, CHCl₃, and THF were examined to check their viability in the reaction. However, an elevated yield was not obtained (entries 2-5 and 6-10). Performing the reaction at elevated temperatures did not significantly influence the outcome of the reaction (entries 11 and 12). When the reaction was carried out without AcOH as the additive, 35% yield of the product **3.1a** was obtained (entry 13). Silver salt is necessary for this transformation, as evident from entry 14. Decreasing the loading of silver salt resulted in lower yields of product **3.1a** (entries 15 and 16). Moreover, on increasing the amount of AcOH, 87% yield of **3.1a** was obtained (entry 17). Furthermore, Cu(OAc)₂ could not effectively mediate the thio-acetoxylation reaction (entry 19).

Table 3.1: Variation of parameters for the synthesis of 3-(p-tolyl)-1,4-benzothiazine^a

Entry	Ag Salt	T (°C)	Solvent	Yield of 3.1a (%)	Yield of 3.2a (%)
1	AgOAc	80	DCE	72	63
2	AgNO ₃	80	DCE	trace	trace
3	AgTFA	80	DCE	39	34
4	AgOTf	80	DCE	trace	trace
5	Ag ₂ CO ₃	80	DCE	21	18
6	AgOAc	80	Toluene	38	33
7	AgOAc	80	MeCN	48	41
8	AgOAc	80	DMSO	ND	ND
9	AgOAc	80	CHCl ₃	trace	trace
10	AgOAc	80	THF	trace	trace

11	AgOAc	100	DCE	85	73
12	AgOAc	120	DCE	80	69
13 ^b	AgOAc	80	DCE	35	30
14	-	80	DCE	ND	ND
15 ^c	AgOAc	80	DCE	16	14
16 ^d	AgOAc	80	DCE	76	65
17^e	AgOAc	80	DCE	87	75
18 ^f	AgOAc	80	DCE	5	trace
19 ^g	-	80	DCE	trace	trace

^a Reaction was carried out at 0.4 mmol scale using 1 equiv. of 2-acetylamino phenyl disulfide, 3 equiv. of 4-methyl styrene, 1.5 equiv. of silver salt, 6 equiv. of AcOH in 2 mL of solvent at the mentioned temperature for 6 hours, unless otherwise noted; the second step: 0.5 ml of TFA was added at room temperature and stirred for 1 hour. ^bAcOH was not used. ^c 0.5 equiv. of AgOAc was used. ^d 1 equiv. of AgOAc was used. ^e 8 equiv. of AcOH was used. ^f 20 mol% of AgOAc was used. ^g Cu(OAc)₂ was used. ND = not detected

3.2.2. Substrate scope of various alkenes

With the optimized reaction conditions in our hand, we then explored the scope of this method with various alkenes. It was found that various aromatic as well as aliphatic alkenes could successfully undergo thio-acetoxylation (Scheme 3.2), followed by cyclization reaction to give the desired products in modest to good yields (Scheme 3.3).

The annulation reaction of *N*-protected aminophenyl disulfide with alkenes proceeded *via* a thio-acetoxylation reaction succeeded by a cyclization triggered by adding 0.5 mL of TFA. Although, most of the thio-acetoxylation products **3.1a-3.1o** were isolated (Scheme 3.2), the second step, annulation, can be carried forward without prior purification of the product obtained from first step through column chromatography. The structure of **3.1h** was further confirmed by a single crystal X-ray diffraction study, which reveals an anti-stereochemistry between arylthio and acetoxy groups in **3.1h** (Figure 3.2).

At first, aromatic alkenes were tested in our reaction conditions (Scheme 3.3). For example, the reaction of 2-acetyl amino phenyl disulfide with methyl styrene gave *N*-acetyl-2,3-dihydro-3-(*p*-tolyl)-1,4-benzothiazine in 75% yield (**3.2a**), whereas the reaction with

styrene gave *N*-acetyl-2,3-dihydro-3-phenyl-1,4-benzothiazine in 38% yield (**3.2b**). The reaction of substituted styrenes, especially with electron-rich substituents such as methyl, methoxy, naphthyl groups (**3.2a**, **3.2e** and **3.2g**) yielded the desired products in modest to good yields (60-75%), whereas electron-deficient substituents such as fluoro and chloro groups (**3.2c**, and **3.2d**) also yielded the products, albeit in moderate amounts (54 and 56%).

Scheme 3.2: Thio-acetoxylation of alkenes

Figure 3.2: Crystal structure of **3.1h**, showing anti-stereochemistry between arylthio and acetoxy groups

Scheme 3.3: 3-Phenyl-1,4-benzothiazine derivatives^a

^a Yield based on isolated **3.1**. ^b Yield based on disulfide

Next, the reaction of 2-acetyl amino phenyl disulfide with aliphatic alkenes was tested. Interestingly, the reactivity of aliphatic alkenes towards this reaction was higher compared to that of styrenes, which was evident from the yields of the respective products. The reaction of 4-vinyl cyclohexane gave a good yield (74%) of *N*-acetyl-2,3-dihydro-3-cyclohexyl-1,4-benzothiazine (**3.2f**), whereas the reaction of *trans*-4-octene produced 72% of the corresponding product (**3.2i**). To check the versatility of the reaction, cyclohexene, an alicyclic alkene, was treated under the optimized reaction conditions, which indeed resulted in a good yield (78%) of the respective product (**3.2h**). 1,5-Cyclooctadiene was also tested as a reactive partner with the disulfide under the same reaction conditions. It gave the thio-acetoxyated product (**3.1m**) in 84% yield (Scheme 3.2); however, the cyclization step resulted in an inseparable mixture. The structures of **3.2a** and **3.2g** are confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction study (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Single crystal structures of **3.2a** and **3.2g**

We then explored 2-benzoylamino phenyl disulfide as the coupling partner with various alkenes (Scheme 3.3). To our delight, this disulfide also reacted smoothly with aromatic, aliphatic as well as alicyclic alkenes, irrespective of their electronic nature under the optimized reaction conditions, to obtain corresponding benzothiazine derivatives (**3.2j-3.2l** and **3.3a-3.3b**) in good yields, as shown in scheme 3.3. The reaction of 4-methyl styrene gave 78% yield of *N*-benzoyl-2,3-dihydro-3-tolyl-1,4-benzothiazine (**3.2j**). 4-Fluoro styrene, an electron poor alkene, reacted smoothly to yield 67% of the respective product **3.3a**, whereas cyclohexene gave 70% of *N*-benzoyl-2,3-dihydro-3-cyclohexyl-1,4-benzothiazine (**3.2l**). Aliphatic alkenes, such as 4-vinyl cyclohexane and *trans*-4-octene, reacted under the optimized conditions to obtain 71% and 82% yields of the cyclized products **3.2k** and **3.3b**, respectively.

An attempted reaction of 2-aminophenyl disulfide, where the amino group is unprotected, was noticed to be sluggish and the desired product could not be obtained, even in trace amounts. Therefore, it appears that *N*-protected disulfides are necessary for this transformation.

3.2.3. Proposed mechanism of the reaction

A plausible mechanism is depicted in Scheme 3.4 based on the obtained results. At first, 2-acetylamino phenyl disulfide on reaction with styrene and silver acetate forms a sulfenyl intermediate **I**, which undergo elimination of silver to form the thio-acetoxyated product **3.1a**. The aryl sulfenyl anion could revert to 2-acetylamino phenyl disulfide. The thio-acetoxyated product on treatment with TFA forms a carbocation **II**, which undergoes deprotonation with a trifluoroacetate ion to evolve our desired product **3.2a**.

Scheme 3.4: Proposed mechanism of C-S and C-N coupling

3.3. Conclusions

We have developed an efficient strategy to obtain the biologically active 3-phenyl benzothiazines using *N*-protected aminophenyl disulfides and alkenes, which involves thio-acetoxylation followed by a cyclization reaction under acidic conditions. This protocol is a convenient entry towards the synthesis of benzothiazine derivatives, having a wide substrate scope of alkenes. We have used aromatic, aliphatic and alicyclic olefins in this reaction to form 3-phenyl 1,4-benzothiazines.

3.4. Experimental section

3.4.1. General experimental details

All NMR experiments were carried out on 400 or 500 MHz spectrometers in CDCl₃ and NMR chemical shifts are reported in ppm, referenced to the solvent peaks of CDCl₃ (7.26 ppm for ¹H and 77.16 (±0.06) ppm for ¹³C). Mass analysis is performed on quadrupole-time of a flight (Q-TOF) mass spectrometer equipped with an ESI source (+ve). 2-Aminothiophenol and all alkenes were used as received from Aldrich and Spectrochem India Pvt. Ltd. 2-aminophenyl disulfide was prepared by the oxidation of respective thiol using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in the presence of a catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine ditelluride. Silica gel (100-200 mesh size) was used for column chromatography. TLC analysis of reaction mixtures was performed using silica gel plates. Synthesis of 2-acetylaminophenyl and 2-

benzoylaminophenyl disulfides was carried out using known procedures in the literature.¹³

3.4.2. Experimental procedures and analytical data

General procedure for the synthesis of (2-((2-acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-(*p*-tolyl)ethyl acetate (3.1a) and 1-(3-(*p*-tolyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-benzo[*b*][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)ethan-1-one (3.2a).

A sealed tube (15 mL) was charged with 2-acetyl amino phenyl disulfide (133 mg, 0.4 mmol), 3-methyl styrene (157 μ l, 1.2 mmol), AgOAc (100 mg, 0.6 mmol), and AcOH (182 μ l, 3.2 mmol) in 2 mL of dry DCE. The resulting reaction mixture was heated for 6 h at 80 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). Then, the reaction mixture was filtered through a thin bed of celite using sintered crucible. The ethyl acetate layer was washed successively with the saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (5 mL x 2) and an aqueous saturated solution of ammonium chloride (5 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 80:20 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford (2-((2-acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-(*p*-tolyl)ethyl acetate, **3.1a** (119 mg, 87% yield).

The resulting brown oil was taken in 10 mL round bottom flask, charged with 0.5 mL of TFA and stirred for 1 h. After completion of the reaction as analyzed by TLC, the reaction mixture was mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (5 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 90:10 hexanes/ ethyl acetate to afford 1-(3-(*p*-tolyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-benzo[*b*][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)-ethan-1-one, **3.2a** (49 mg, 75% yield).

Preparation of 3.2a without isolation of 3.1a

The crude reaction mixture of **3.1a** before column chromatography (*vide supra*) was treated with 0.5 mL of TFA and stirred for 1 h. Workup and purification are similar as that described above. **3.2a** (91 mg, 80% Yield).

(2-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-(*p*-tolyl)ethyl acetate (3.1a).

Yellow oil. Yield 119 mg (87%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.35 (bs, 1H), 8.32 (s, 1H), 7.49 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.29 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.13 (m, 4H), 7.02 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 3.26 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H), 3.07 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 2.31 (s, 3H), 2.14 (s, 3H), 1.98 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.2, 168.5, 139.6, 138.5, 135.5, 135.2, 129.9, 129.4, 126.6, 124.3, 122.4, 120.5, 74.6, 42.1, 24.8, 21.2, 21.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 366.1141 (Calculated for C₁₉H₂₁NO₃S + Na⁺: 366.1134).

(2-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-phenylethyl acetate (3.1b)

Brown oil. Yield 120 mg (91%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.35 (bs, 1H), 8.32 (s, 1H), 7.48 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.29 (m, 4H), 7.25 (m, 2H), 7.02 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 5.85 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 3.27 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H), 3.08 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 2.14 (s, 3H), 1.98 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.2, 168.5, 139.6, 138.5, 135.2, 129.9, 128.7, 128.6, 126.6, 124.3, 122.3, 120.6, 74.7, 42.2, 24.8, 21.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 352.1003 (Calculated for C₁₈H₁₉NO₃S + Na⁺: 352.0978).

(2-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl acetate (3.1c)

Brown oil. Yield 90 mg (65%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.34 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 8.30 (bs, 1H), 7.32 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (m, 2H), 7.01 (m, 3H), 5.82 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 5.2 Hz, 1H), 3.25 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 2.17 (s, 3H), 2.00 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.1, 168.5, 135.2, 134.4, 134.3, 130.1, 128.5, 128.4, 124.3, 120.6, 115.7, 115.5, 74.0, 42.0, 24.8, 21.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 370.0912 (Calculated for C₁₈H₁₈FNO₃S + Na⁺: 370.0884).

(2-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)ethyl acetate (3.1d)

Brown oil. Yield 109 mg (75%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.38 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 8.32 (bs, 1H), 7.50 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (m, 3H), 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.07 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 5.83 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 5.2 Hz, 1H), 3.27 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H), 3.08 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 2.20 (s, 3H), 2.03 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.0, 168.5, 139.5, 137.0, 135.2, 134.5, 130.1, 128.9, 128.0, 124.3, 122.0, 120.6, 74.0, 41.9, 24.8, 21.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 386.0603 (Calculated for C₁₈H₁₈ClNO₃S + Na⁺: 386.0588).

(Z)-8-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)cyclooct-4-en-1-yl acetate (3.1m)

Brown oil. Yield 112 mg (84%); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.52 (bs, 1H), 8.39 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.48 (m, 1H), 7.31 (m, 1H), 7.02 (t, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 5.65 (m, 1H), 5.53 (m, 1H), 5.14 (m, 1H), 3.35 (m, 1H), 2.49 (m, 1H), 2.34 (m, 1H), 2.24 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 3H), 2.17 (m, 2H), 2.09 (m, 1H), 2.05 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 3H), 1.98 (m, 1H), 1.77 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.2, 168.4, 139.9, 135.9, 129.9, 129.8, 128.0, 123.9, 122.0, 120.1, 75.8, 52.8, 32.0, 31.4, 24.9, 24.5, 23.5, 21.1; HRMS-ESI m/z : 334.1483 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_3\text{S} + \text{H}^+$: 334.1471).

(2-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-1-phenylpropyl acetate (3.1n)

Yellow oil. Yield 106 mg (78%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.41 (bs, 1H), 8.39 (s, 1H), 7.49 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.34 (m, 4H), 7.26 (m, 2H), 7.05 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 5.89 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.32 (qt, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.17 (s, 3H), 2.13 (s, 3H), 1.32 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.0, 168.3, 140.1, 137.9, 136.4, 130.3, 128.4, 128.3, 126.7, 124.0, 121.0, 120.0, 76.8, 50.6, 24.9, 21.0, 16.5.

3-((2-Acetamidophenyl)thio)-2-methylbutan-2-yl acetate (3.1o)

Yellow oil. Yield 50 mg (68%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.54 (bs, 1H), 8.45 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.52 (dd, $J = 7.6, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.35 (dt, $J = 7.6, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.04 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.89 (q, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H), 2.28 (s, 3H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 3H), 1.56 (s, 3H), 1.18 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.7, 168.6, 140.5, 137.0, 130.2, 123.7, 120.8, 120.1, 84.3, 52.1, 24.8, 24.2, 23.4, 22.2, 17.1.

1-(3-(*p*-Tolyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-benzo[*b*][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)ethan-1-one (3.2a)

Brown oil. Yield 49 mg (75%); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36 (m, 1H), 7.18 (m, 5H), 7.08 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 6.21 (bs, 1H), 3.54 (dd, $J = 13.0, 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (dd, $J = 13.0, 7.9$ Hz, 1H), 2.29 (s, 3H), 2.12 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.1, 138.1, 137.1, 136.9, 133.3, 129.2, 128.9, 128.3, 126.6, 126.4, 126.1, 57.1, 36.0, 23.1, 21.1; HRMS-ESI m/z : 284.1125 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{NOS} + \text{H}^+$: 284.1104).

1-(3-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-benzo[*b*][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)ethan-1-one (3.2b)

Brown oil. Yield 41 mg (38%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.37 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.20 (bs, 1H), 7.47 (dd, $J = 7.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.36 (m, 4H), 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.05 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 5.88 (dd, $J = 8.6, 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 3.36 (dd, $J = 14.1, 8.5$ Hz, 1H),

3.16 (dd, $J = 14.1, 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.15 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 168.4, 139.6, 136.0, 135.2, 130.5, 129.6, 129.1, 126.6, 124.4, 120.7, 78.5, 41.4, 24.8; HRMS-ESI m/z : 269.0953 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{NOS} + \text{H}^+$: 269.0947)

1-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,3-dihydro-4H-benzo[b][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)ethan-1-one (3.2c)

Yellow semi-solid. Yield 37 mg (54%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.27 (m, 1H), 7.17 (m, 2H), 7.08 (m, 3H), 6.86 (m, 2H), 6.12 (bs, 1H), 3.46 (dd, $J = 13.0, 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.04 (dd, $J = 13.2, 7.5$ Hz, 1H), 2.03 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.1, 137.8, 135.6, 128.9, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 126.6, 126.2, 115.5, 115.3, 56.6, 35.8, 23.0; HRMS-ESI m/z : 310.0672 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{FNOS} + \text{Na}^+$: 310.0672).

1-(3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2,3-dihydro-4H-benzo[b][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)ethan-1-one (3.2d)

Yellow oil. Yield 39 mg (56%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.58 (bs, 1H), 8.34 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.52 (dd, $J = 7.8, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.34 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.21 (m, 2H), 7.05 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 4.62 (dd, $J = 9.0, 3.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.05 (dd, $J = 13.6, 3.7$ Hz, 1H), 2.93 (dd, $J = 13.6, 9.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.18 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 168.6, 140.5, 139.9, 136.6, 135.6, 134.0, 130.3, 128.8, 127.3, 124.3, 120.9, 71.3, 45.1, 24.8 ; HRMS-ESI m/z : 304.0579 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNOS} + \text{H}^+$: 304.0557).

(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,3-dihydro-4H-benzo[b][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)(phenyl)methanone (3.3a)

Yellow oil. Yield 93 mg (67%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.27 (m, 6H), 7.16 (m, 2H), 6.96 (m, 3H), 6.77 (dt, $J = 7.8, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.55 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.20 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.65 (dd, $J = 13.1, 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.23 (dd, $J = 13.1, 7.5$ Hz, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 168.6, 140.5, 139.9, 136.6, 135.6, 134.0, 130.3, 128.8, 127.3, 124.3, 120.9, 71.3, 45.1, 24.8 ; HRMS-ESI m/z : 372.0844 (Calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{FNOS} + \text{Na}^+$: 372.0829).

(2,3-Dipropyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-benzo[b][1,4]thiazin-4-yl)(phenyl)methanone (3.3b)

Yellow semi-solid. Yield 83 mg (82%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.29 (bs, 1H), 8.55 (dd, $J = 8.4, 1.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.93 (m, 2H), 7.56 (m, 2H), 7.49 (m, 2H), 7.41 (dt, $J = 7.8, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.09 (dt, $J = 7.6, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 5.20 (m, 1H), 2.95 (td, $J = 9.6, 3.1$ Hz, 1H), 1.78 (m, 1H), 1.64 (m, 2H), 1.50 (m, 2H), 1.32 (m, 1H), 1.19 (m, 2H), 0.80 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 165.3, 140.0, 136.3, 134.9, 132.0, 130.6,

128.8, 127.1, 124.4, 121.9, 120.7, 79.9, 33.1, 31.6, 20.9, 18.7, 13.7, 13.5; HRMS-ESI m/z : 340.1757 (Calculated for $C_{21}H_{25}NOS + H^+$: 340.1730).

Table 3.2: The crystallographic details of compounds **3.1h**, **3.2a** and **3.2g**

Compound	3.1h	3.2a	3.2g
Molecular formula	$C_{16}H_{21}NO_3S$	$C_{17}H_{17}NOS$	$C_{20}H_{17}NOS$
Molecular weight	307.40	283.37	319.40
CCDC number	1409837	1409829	1409828
a(Å), b(Å), c(Å), V(Å³)	9.3777(6), 9.5320(6), 34.929(2), 3122.2(3)	6.2101(4), 21.6012(15), 10.6587(8), 1429.82(17)	16.3601(8), 6.1956(3), 16.4686(8), 1586.29(13)
α, β, γ (°)	90, 90, 90	90, 90, 90	90, 108.14, 90
Crystal System	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic	Monoclinic
Space Group	$Pna2_1$	$Pna2_1$	$P2_1/c$
T (K)	296(2) K	301(2) K	296(2) K
Z	8	4	4
ρ (g/cm³)	1.308	1.316	1.337
μ (mm⁻¹)	0.217	0.221	0.208
F (000)	1312	600	672
θ min, max (°)	1.166, 26.055	2.131, 25.053	1.310, 25.717
h; k; l (min, max)	-11, 11; -10, 11; -42, 43	-7, 7; -25, 25; -12, 12	-19, 19; -7, 7; -19, 20
No. of reflections	22493	16452	14231
R (int)	0.0441	0.0617	0.0178
No. of parameters	383	183	209
R₁ all, R₁ obs	0.0528, 0.0391	0.0499, 0.0357	0.0419, 0.0352
wR₂ all, wR₂ obs	0.1055, 0.0849	0.0847, 0.0789	0.0972, 0.0921
G. F.	1.072	1.050	1.038

3.5. Representative NMR spectra of thio-acetoxyated products

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.1a

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound 3.1b

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.1m

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.1o

3.6. Representative NMR spectra of benzothiazines

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.2a

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.2b

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 3.2m

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound 3.2n

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CHAPTER 4

Transition-Metal-Free Intermolecular Selective Oxidative C(sp³)-H Functionalization: Synthesis of 3-Sulfonyl Oxindoles, Sulfenyl and Selenenyl Heterocycles

Abstract:

A transition metal free synthetic method has been developed for the synthesis of novel 3-sulfonyl oxindoles using potassium iodide, TBHP as oxidant in DMSO and acetic acid. The reaction system was tolerable to make different variety of sulfonated products. Similarly, another transition metal free method has been devised for the preparation of 3-sulfenyl and 3-selenenyl oxindoles using KO^tBu in DMSO as the solvent, which exhibited broad substrate scope in terms of substituted oxindoles and disulfides. Moreover, 3-chalcogenation of 2-phenylacetamide was achieved. α -Tetralone, a cyclic ketone underwent concomitant chalcogenation and aromatization resulted in 2-chalcogenyl-1-naphthols. Furthermore, the synthesized 3-sulfonyl oxindoles were transformed to 3-sulfonyl indoles using Schwartz reagent.

4.1. Introduction

Oxindoles are an important class of heterocycles that are frequently found in many natural products and biologically active compounds.¹ In particular, the functionalized oxindoles have aroused a significant synthetic interest because of their important applications in asymmetric synthesis, library design and drug discovery.² Especially, oxindoles with a heteroatom at the C-3 position have received a considerable attention owing to their potential applications in medicinal chemistry.³ Many oxindoles with a thio or sulfonyl group at the *sp*³ carbon centre have been found to have anticancer, antifungal, or antitubercular activities (Figure 4.1).^{3e-g} In addition, they were used widely as building blocks for the asymmetric synthesis of biologically interesting 3-sulfonyl substituted quaternary stereocenters.

Figure 4.1: Bioactive 3-sulfonyl and 3-sulfenyl oxindoles

Therefore, the synthesis of 3-sulfonyloxindoles has been explored and a handful approaches have been developed.⁴ For example, Procter et al. successfully used the Pummer reaction for the efficient synthesis of 3-sulfonyloxindoles by employing various thiols and glyoxamides as precursors.^{4d-g} In 2011, Zhang et al. developed a Rh-(OAc)₂-catalyzed thia-Sommelet–Hauser rearrangement that led to the formation of 3-arylthiooxindoles in moderate to good yields.^{4h} In all these procedures, the use of the pre-functionalized substrates is necessary to get 3-arylthiooxindoles. To the best of our knowledge, there has been no literature route, where sulfonyl group can be directly incorporated into the oxindole framework without the use of pre-functionalized precursors.

The sulfone functionality on the other hand, is the key structural motif, widely exists in a variety of natural products, clinical pharmaceuticals, and synthetic intermediates.⁵ The incorporation of the sulfone group into organic molecules has drawn increasing attention from scientists in view of their important biological properties and widespread synthetic applications for various organic transformations.⁶ In recent years, the direct sulfonylation

via C–H functionalization has attracted great interest since this method can potentially lead to more efficient synthesis with a reduced number of synthetic operations in an atom economical manner.⁷ Among the various sulfonylation reagents employed, sodium sulfonates are stable and easy to handle, and they have been widely used as sulfonylating agents.⁸

Although, a few elegant synthetic methods have been realized for the synthesis of sulfonated oxindoles via arylsulfonylation of *N*-acrylamides utilizing either transition-metal catalysed or metal-free oxidative difunctionalization of activated alkenes,⁹ there has been no report of direct sulfonylation of oxindole moiety at the *sp*³ carbon centre to date. Owing to our continued interest in the construction of organosulfur heterocyclic compounds,¹⁰ herein, we wish to report a new and efficient transition-metal-free approach for the direct sulfonylation of oxindoles with sodium sulfonates as sulfonylating agents towards the construction of novel sulfonyl oxindoles. Further, synthesized 3-sulfonyl oxindoles were transformed to 3-sulfonyl indoles using Schwartz reagent. Also, a transition-metal free method has been developed for the construction of 3-sulphenyl and 3-selenenyl oxindoles.

4.2. Results and discussion

4.2.1. Survey of the reaction conditions for the sulfonylation reaction

Initially, a model reaction of oxindole with sodium *p*-toluene sulfonate was conducted in DMSO-AcOH (1:1) in the presence of KI (1 equiv.) at 80 °C. Indeed, the desired sulfonyl oxindole **4.1a** was obtained in 32% yield (Table 4.1, entry 1). The optimization results were enlisted in Table 4.1. To our delight, 70% yield of the desired product was obtained when the same reaction was performed in the presence of TBHP (1 equiv.) as oxidant (entry 2). A reaction without KI resulted in the formation of no desired product (entry 3). Then, the effect of other iodine sources such as NaI and I₂ was investigated. It was observed that NaI could also mediate the sulfonylation reaction to give the product **4.1a** in 61% yield, while I₂ could not afford the desired product (entries 4–5). A catalytic amount of KI could only give the trace amount of the desired product (entry 6). Further, the sulfonylation reaction which was performed in other solvents such as EtOH and DCE, could not provide the elevated yield of **3a** (entries 7–8). The desired product **4.1a** was obtained in trace amounts, when the reaction was performed in AcOH alone (entry 9). In contrast, the reaction which was performed in DMSO alone, could not give the desired product (entry 10). The sulfonylation reaction performed at room temperature gave poor yield of **4.1a**; whereas

altering the reaction temperature above or below 80 °C could not provide the best yield of the desired product (entries 11-13).

Table 4.1: Synthesis of 3-tosylindolin-2-one: Survey of the reaction conditions^a

S. No.	Deviation from above conditions	Yield of 4.1a (%)
1	without TBHP	32
2	above standard conditions	70
3	without KI	ND
4	NaI instead of KI	61
5	I ₂ instead of KI	ND
6	KI (0.2 mol%)	trace
7	EtOH as solvent	15
8	DCE as solvent	5
9	AcOH as solvent	trace
10	DMSO as solvent	ND
11	at room temperature	12
12	at 60 °C	65
13	at 100 °C	68

^a Reaction was carried out using oxindole (0.20 mmol), sodium *p*-toluene sulfinate (0.4 mmol), iodine source (1 equiv.), TBHP (1 equiv.) in solvent (1 mL) at 80 °C for 4 h. ND = not detected.

4.2.2. Substrate scope of various oxindoles and aryl sulfinates

With the optimized reaction conditions in our hand, we investigated the scope of oxindoles in the current reaction system (Scheme 4.1). In most cases, oxindoles were smoothly converted to corresponding sulfonated oxindoles in moderate to good yields. Oxindoles with free N-H group as well as *N*-protected groups reacted well and respective sulfonated products (**4.1a-4.1l**) were obtained. For example, the reaction of 3-methyl oxindole with sodium *p*-toluene sulfinate gave 3-methyl-3-tosylindolin-2-one (**4.1b**) in 47% yield, whereas the reaction with methane sulfinate gave 3-methyl-3-(methylsulfonyl)indolin-2-

one in 39% yield (**4.1c**). The reaction of oxindole with methane sulfinate afforded 3-(methylsulfonyl)indolin-2-one in 57% yield (**4.1d**).

Next, the reaction of *N*-methyl oxindole with sodium *p*-toluene sulfinate gave 1-methyl-3-tosylindolin-2-one in 58% yield (**4.1e**), while the reaction with sodium benzene sulfinate provided 1-methyl-3-(phenylsulfonyl)indolin-2-one in 70% yield (**4.1f**).

Scheme 4.1: Scope of 3-sulfonyl oxindoles

^a Reaction was carried out at using oxindole (0.5 mmol), sulfinate salt (1 mmol), KI (1 equiv.), TBHP (1 equiv.) in AcOH:DMSO = 1:1 (1 mL) at 80 °C for 4 h.

Figure 4.2: Crystal structure of **4.1a**

Later, the scope of *N*-methyl oxindoles having substituents on the phenyl ring was checked under the optimized reaction conditions of the sulfonylation reaction. Irrespective of the electronic effect of the substituent attached to the phenyl ring, corresponding sulfonated products were formed in decent yields. The reaction of *N*-methyl oxindoles with electron-deficient substituents such as bromo and chloro, resulted in 59% and 66% yields of the respective sulfonated products (**4.1g**, **4.1i-4.1k**). In case of the reaction with electron-rich methoxy group substituted *N*-methyl oxindole, it gave the poor yield of the desired product (**4.1h**). The same reaction of oxindole with free *N*-H group, gave the 58% yield of the desired product (**4.1l**). 3-benzyl oxindole was not compatible in the sulfonylation reaction to give quarternary centered 3-sulfonyl oxindole, as it led to many side products. Further, the structure of 3-tosylindolin-2-one (**4.1a**) was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction study (figure 4.2).¹¹

4.2.3. Chalcogenation of oxindole

Afterwards, we turned our attention to synthesize 3-sulfenyl oxindoles as these compounds are biologically important as well (*vide supra*). We attempted the sulfenylation reaction with disulfides under the optimized potassium iodide mediated conditions. Unfortunately, the sulfenylation reaction was not clean in this case, giving many spots on TLC. Instead, we thought a base can promote the sulfenylation reaction in an electrophilic pathway to give 3-sulfenyl oxindoles with thiols or disulfides.

As we already explored KO^tBu as a promoter in coupling reactions,¹² we tried the sulfenylation reaction of oxindole with thiol using KO^tBu. It gave the sulfenated product in low yield, as the formation of substantial amount of respective disulfide in the reaction was

noticed. Hence, disulfide was used as the source of sulfur moiety. Indeed, a considerable increase in the yield of the product was observed. After a bit of tuning of the stoichiometry of the reagents for the sulfenylation reaction, it was noticed that employing 1 equiv. of disulfide, 3 equiv. of oxindole and 1.5 equiv. of KO^tBu in 1.5 mL of DMSO at room temperature gave respective 3-sulfonyl oxindoles in quantitative yields. With these conditions in our hand, we then explored the scope of this method utilizing various disulfides. It was found that differently substituted disulfides are compatible in this reaction and afforded structurally diverse 3-sulfonyl oxindoles in an excellent yields (Scheme 4.2).

Scheme 4.2: 3-sulfonyl/3-selenenyl oxindoles.

^a Reaction was carried out at using aryl disulfide (0.3 mmol), oxindole (0.9 mmol), KO^tBu (1.5 equiv) in DMSO (1 mL) at room temperature for 6 h.

At first, various aromatic disulfides were tested under our reaction conditions. For example, the reaction of 2-oxindole with phenyl disulfide gave 3-(phenylthio)indolin-2-one (**4.2a**) in 83% yield, whereas the reaction with *p*-tolyl disulfide provided 3-(*p*-tolylthio)indolin-2-one (**4.2b**) in 78% yield. The reaction of substituted phenyl disulfides especially with electron-poor substituents such as chloro, fluoro groups resulted in excellent outcome of the corresponding 3-sulfenyl indoles (**4.2c** and **4.2d**). An attempted reaction of oxindole with an aliphatic substrate, *n*-hexyl disulfide was also successful to afford 3-(hexylthio)indolin-2-one (**4.2e**), albeit in low yield. Likewise, a reaction of oxindole with a hetero-aromatic substrate, 2-pyridyl disulfide gave 3-(pyridin-2-ylthio)indolin-2-one (**4.2f**) in 82% yield. Then, the scope of *N*-methyl oxindoles and free *N*-H oxindoles having substituents on the phenyl ring, was tested to check the viability of the current reaction system. The reaction of oxindoles with electron-deficient substituents such as 5-bromo and 5-chloro groups, resulted in good to excellent yields of the respective sulfenylated products (**4.2g-4.2i**). The beauty of this reaction system lies in its successful extension to prepare the quaternary centered 3-sulfenyl oxindoles. 3-benzyl oxindole, on reaction with phenyl disulfide provided 3-benzyl-3-(phenylthio)indolin-2-one (**4.2j**) in 90% yield. The substituents on either phenyl ring of oxindole or that of disulfide could not affect much on the elegance of the current reaction system to afford corresponding 3,3-disubstituted sulfenyl products (**4.2k-4.2l**).

Later, we thought it would be facile to incorporate selenium into the oxindole moiety using the present method. Gratifyingly, phenyl diselenide was also compatible with the reaction system (Scheme 4.2). 3-benzyl oxindoles, on reaction with phenyl diselenide gave respective selenenyl products in modest yields (**4.2m-4.2o**). Similarly, a reaction with *N*-methyl oxindole gave 3-methyl-3-(phenylselanyl)indolin-2-one (**4.2o**) in 44% yield. Unfortunately, phenyl ditelluride could not afford the respective tellurated oxindole; instead, 3-hydroxy oxindole product was formed as the major product.

4.2.4. Chalcogenation of 2-phenylacetamide

To check the versatility of the present reaction system, we attempted a reaction of linear substrate, 2-phenylacetamide with phenyl dichalcogenides. Indeed, the desired α -chalcogenated products **4.3a-4.3c** were obtained in moderate to good yields (Scheme 4.3).

Scheme 4.3: Chalcogenation of 2-phenylacetamide^a

^a The reaction was carried out using aryl dichalcogenide (0.5 mmol), *N,N*-diisopropyl-2-phenylacetamide (1 mmol), KO^tBu (1.5 equiv.) in DMSO (1.5 mL) at room temperature for 6 h.

4.2.5. Chalcogenation of α -tetralone

α -tetralone, a cyclic ketone was also tested under the current reaction conditions. Unexpectedly, it resulted in the formation of 2-chalcogenyl-1-naphthol (**4.4**), by concomitant chalcogenation and aromatization (Scheme 4.4). These products, mainly selenium compounds are proved to be good anti-oxidants.¹³ Here, we could access 2-chalcogenyl-1-naphthols (**4.4a-4.4c**) in decent yields.

Scheme 4.4: Chalcogenation of α -tetralone.

^a Reaction was carried out using aryl dichalcogenide (0.5 mmol), α -tetralone (1 mmol), KO^tBu (1.5 equiv) in DMSO (1.5 mL) at room temperature for 6 h

4.2.6. Synthetic elaboration of 3-sulfonyl oxindole

The synthetic utility of the synthesized 3-sulfonyl oxindoles was then explored by using Schwartz reagent to obtain respective 3-sulfonyl indoles (Scheme 4.5). 3-tosylindolin-2-one

(**4.1a**), on reaction with Schwartz reagent, provided 3-tosyl-1*H*-indole (**4.5a**) in 63% yield. Similarly, 5-chloro-1-methyl-3-tosyl-1*H*-indole (**4.5b**) can be obtained in 60% yield.

Scheme 4.5: Further elaboration of synthesized 3-sulfonyl oxindoles to 3-sulfonyl indoles.^a

^a Reaction was carried out using 3-sulfonyl oxindole (0.2 mmol), Cp_2ZrHCl (0.4 mmol) in THF (2 mL) at room temperature for 2 h.

4.2.7. Plausible mechanism for the sulfonylation of oxindole

A plausible mechanism for the sulfonylation reaction could be depicted (Scheme 4.6) based on the obtained results and previous literature reports.^{8h}

Scheme 4.6: Proposed mechanism for the sulfonylation reaction

In the presence of TBHP, iodide can be converted to iodine radical. At the expense of iodide radical, aryl sulfinate ion could be transformed by single electron transfer (SET), forming radical species **C**, which in turn lead to radical species **D**. In the presence of acid, oxindole reversibly forms species **A**. This species reacts with sulfur radical **D** to form radical species **B**, which can be trapped with iodine radical to obtain our desired product **4.1a**, by the elimination of molecule of HI.

4.2.8. Plausible mechanism for the sulfenylation of oxindole

Scheme 4.7: Plausible mechanism for the sulfenylation reaction

In the pathway of sulfenylation reaction (Scheme 4.7), oxindole undergoes deprotonation in the presence of KO^tBu to form α -carbanion, that tautomerizes to oxy anion, which on reaction with dichalcogenide forms the desired product **4.2a**. On the other hand, phenyl chalcogenide ion reacts with *tert*-butanol yielding chalcogenol, which oxidizes in presence of air or DMSO to form dichalcogenide again.

4.3. Conclusions

To conclude, we have developed an accessible transition-metal free synthetic method for the synthesis of novel 3-sulfonyl oxindoles using potassium iodide, TBHP as oxidant in DMSO and acetic acid. The reaction system is compatible to make a library of sulfonated oxindole products. Further, synthesized 3-sulfonyl oxindoles were transformed to 3-sulfonyl indoles using Schwartz reagent in THF. Similarly, we have also presented another transition metal free method for the preparation of novel 3-sulfenyl and 3-selenenyl oxindoles using KO^tBu in DMSO. This reaction exhibited broad substrate scope in terms of substituted oxindoles and disulfides. Moreover, 3-chalcogenation of 2-phenylacetamide was also achieved. α -Tetralone gave 2-chalcogenyl-1-naphthols *via* concomitant chalcogenation and aromatization. These developed methods are significant owing to their potentially simple operational procedures.

4.4. Experimental section

4.4.1. General experimental details

All NMR experiments were carried out on 400 or 500 MHz spectrometers in CDCl_3 or DMSO-d_6 and NMR chemical shifts are reported in ppm, referenced to the solvent peaks of CDCl_3 (7.26 ppm for ^1H and 77.16 (± 0.06) ppm for ^{13}C) or DMSO-d_6 (2.50 ppm for ^1H and 39.50 ppm for ^{13}C). Mass analysis is performed on quadrupole-time of a flight (Q-TOF) mass spectrometer equipped with an ESI source (+ve/-ve) or

atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) source. 2-oxindole, sodium sulfinate salts and α -tetralone were used as received from Aldrich and Spectrochem India Pvt. Ltd. Substituted oxindoles were prepared by using reported literature procedures.¹⁴ Substituted aryl disulfides were prepared by the oxidation of respective thiols by using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in the presence of a catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine ditelluride. Silica gel (100-200 mesh size) was used for the column chromatography. TLC analysis of reaction mixtures was performed using silica gel plates.

4.4.2. Experimental procedures and analytical data

4.4.2.1. General procedure for the synthesis of 3-tosylindolin-2-one (4.1a)

A sealed tube (15 mL) was charged with 2-oxindole (67 mg, 0.5 mmol), sodium *p*-toluene sulfinate (178 mg, 1 mmol), KI (83 mg, 0.5 mmol), TBHP (65 μ l, 0.5 mmol) in 0.5 mL of AcOH and 0.5 mL of DMSO. The resulting reaction mixture was heated for 4 h at 80 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was extracted successively with the saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (5 mL x 2), an aqueous saturated solution of sodium chloride (5 mL x 2) and water (20 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 65:35 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford 3-tosylindolin-2-one, **4.1a** (101 mg, 70% yield), brick red solid; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.67 (bs, 1H), 7.53 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.34 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 3H), 7.26 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.01 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 5.65 (s, 1H), 2.34 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) δ 168.4, 145.5, 143.8, 134.5, 130.7, 129.9, 129.4, 127.1, 122.4, 119.9, 110.3, 68.2, 21.6; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 288.0695 (Calculated for C₁₅H₁₃NO₃S + H⁺: 288.0689).

3-Methyl-3-tosylindolin-2-one (4.1b)

White solid. Yield 70 mg (47%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.68 (bs, 1H), 7.44 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.33 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.32 – 7.28 (m, 1H), 7.10 – 7.06 (m, 1H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 2.37 (s, 3H), 1.71 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 172.1, 145.6, 143.0, 132.2, 130.9, 130.4, 129.6, 126.4, 124.8, 122.5, 110.3, 70.8, 21.6, 16.7; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 302.0856 (Calculated for C₁₆H₁₅NO₃S + H⁺: 302.0845).

3-Methyl-3-(methylsulfonyl)indolin-2-one (4.1c)

Brick red solid. Yield 35 mg (39%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.43 (bs, 1H), 7.53 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (td, *J* = 7.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 7.12 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 6.92 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 3.07 (s, 3H), 1.90 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.2, 141.2, 130.8, 126.4, 123.6, 110.5, 69.9, 35.7, 18.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 226.0507 (Calculated for C₁₀H₁₁NO₃S + H⁺: 226.0532).

3-(Methylsulfonyl)indolin-2-one (4.1d)

Yellow semi-solid. Yield 30 mg (57%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.99 (bs, 1H), 7.44 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.36 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.07 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 6.94 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 5.61 (s, 1H), 3.29 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) δ 169.7, 144.2, 130.7, 127.1, 122.5, 119.0, 110.5, 66.6, 39.9; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 234.0204 (Calculated for C₉H₉NO₃S + Na⁺: 234.0195).

1-Methyl-3-tosylindolin-2-one (4.1e)

Brick red solid. Yield 90 mg (58%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.68 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.58 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.35 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 6.68 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 4.90 (s, 1H), 3.00 (s, 3H), 2.38 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.7, 145.5, 144.8, 133.3, 130.6, 129.5, 129.3, 127.2, 123.2, 118.3, 108.4, 68.3, 26.4, 21.7; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 302.0854 (Calculated for C₁₆H₁₅NO₃S + H⁺: 302.0845).

4.4.2.2. General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(phenylthio)indolin-2-one (4.2a)

A round bottom flask (10 mL) was charged with 2-oxindole (120 mg, 0.9 mmol), diphenyl disulfide (65 mg, 0.3 mmol), KO^tBu (50 mg, 0.45 mmol) in 1 mL of DMSO. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was extracted with an aqueous saturated solution of sodium chloride or brine solution (5 mL x 2) and water (20 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 80:20 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford 3-(phenylthio)indolin-2-one, **4.2a** (60 mg, 83% yield), white solid; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.17 (bs, 1H), 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 2H), 7.34 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.23 – 7.12 (m, 4H), 7.02 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 6.77 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 4.57 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.3, 141.4, 133.9, 131.1, 129.1, 128.8, 128.6, 126.8, 125.5, 122.8, 110.2, 49.7; LRMS-ESI *m/z*: 240.1 (Calculated for C₁₄H₁₁NOS - H⁺: 240.1).

3-(*p*-Tolylthio)indolin-2-one (4.2b)

Pale red solid. Yield 60 mg (78%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.92 (bs, 1H), 7.34 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.25 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.16 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.03 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 6.95 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 6.75 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 4.51 (s, 1H), 2.23 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.1, 141.3, 138.9, 134.4, 129.6, 129.0, 127.1, 127.0, 125.5, 1227, 110.1, 50.0, 21.2; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 256.0798 (Calculated for C₁₅H₁₃NOS + H⁺: 256.0791)

3-Benzyl-5-chloro-3-((4-methoxyphenyl)thio)indolin-2-one (4.2l)

Yellow solid. Yield 30 mg (76%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.04 (bs, 1H), 7.29 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.06 (dd, *J* = 5.0, 1.8 Hz, 3H), 7.03 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 6.95 (m, 2H), 6.65 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.42 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 3.44 (d, *J* = 13.4 Hz, 1H), 3.30 (d, *J* = 13.4 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.5, 161.0, 138.8, 138.3, 134.6, 131.4, 130.1, 128.6, 128.1, 127.6, 127.0, 125.5, 119.7, 114.2, 110.6, 60.5, 55.2, 40.9; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 396.0809 (Calculated for C₂₂H₁₈ClNO₂S + H⁺: 396.0820)

3-Benzyl-3-(phenylselanyl)indolin-2-one (4.2m)

Yellow solid. Yield 20 mg (53%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.00 (bs, 1H), 7.42 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.17 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.07 (m, 4H), 7.02 (m, 3H), 6.53 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.59 (d, *J* = 13.6 Hz, 1H), 3.52 (d, *J* = 13.6 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 178.4, 140.0, 137.7, 135.8, 130.0, 129.46, 129.42, 128.6, 128.4, 128.0, 126.8, 126.1, 125.1, 122.2, 109.7, 54.1, 40.5 ; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 380.0542 (Calculated for C₂₁H₁₇NOSe + H⁺: 380.0549)

3-Methyl-3-(phenylselanyl)indolin-2-one (4.2o)

Red viscous oil. Yield 20 mg (44%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.29 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 7.17 (t, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 7.12 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.01 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 4.67 (s, 1H), 2.92 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.2, 143.8, 136.3, 128.9, 128.6, 128.5, 127.0, 125.7, 125.2, 122.6, 107.9, 41.2, 26.1 ; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 304.0253 (Calculated for C₁₅H₁₃NOSe + H⁺: 304.0236)

4.4.2.3. General procedure for the synthesis of *N,N*-diisopropyl-2-phenyl-2-(phenylthio)acetamide (4.3a)

A round bottom flask (10 mL) was charged with *N,N*-diisopropyl-2-phenylacetamide (219 mg, 1 mmol), diphenyl disulfide (109 mg, 0.5 mmol), KO^tBu (84 mg, 0.75 mmol) in 1.5 mL

of DMSO. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was extracted with an aqueous saturated solution of sodium chloride or brine solution (5 mL x 2) and water (20 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 80:20 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford *N,N*-diisopropyl-2-phenyl-2-(phenylthio)acetamide, **4.3a** (90 mg, 55% yield), white solid; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.28 – 7.18 (m, 8H), 5.09 (s, 1H), 3.98 – 3.89 (m, 1H), 3.34 (bs, 1H), 1.47 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 1.40 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 1.10 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 0.66 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 167.7, 138.0, 134.6, 133.7, 128.7, 128.5, 128.1, 127.7, 127.6, 59.6, 49.2, 46.4, 20.7, 20.6, 19.9, 19.8 ; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 328.1758 (Calculated for C₂₀H₂₅NOS + H⁺: 328.1730).

***N*-isopropyl-2-phenyl-2-(*p*-tolylthio)acetamide (4.3b)**

White solid. Yield 81 mg (54%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.30 (m, 3H), 7.25 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.08 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 6.71 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1 H), 4.86 (s, 1H), 4.04 (m, 1H), 2.30 (s, 3H), 1.12 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.02 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 168.2, 137.6, 136.5, 130.8 (2), 130.0, 128.8, 128.2, 128.1, 58.0, 41.8, 22.6, 22.4, 21.1; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 300.1437 (Calculated for C₁₈H₂₁NOS + H⁺: 300.1417).

***N*-isopropyl-2-phenyl-2-(phenylselanyl)acetamide (4.3c)**

White solid. Yield 60 mg (72%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.50 (m, 2H), 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.30 (m, 6H), 6.28 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.97 (s, 1H), 4.05 (m, 1H), 1.13 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.05 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 168.4, 137.1, 134.1, 129.6, 129.2, 128.8, 128.4, 128.2, 127.9, 52.1, 42.0, 22.6, 22.4; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 334.0713 (Calculated for C₁₇H₁₉NOSe + H⁺: 334.0705).

4.4.2.4. General procedure for the synthesis of 2-(*p*-tolylthio)naphthalene-1-ol (4.4a)

A round bottom flask (10 mL) was charged with α-tetralone (134 μl, 1 mmol), diphenyl disulfide (109 mg, 0.5 mmol), KO^tBu (84 mg, 0.75 mmol) in 1.5 mL of DMSO. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was extracted with an aqueous saturated solution of sodium chloride or brine solution (5 mL x 2) and water (20 mL x 2).

The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 95:5 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford 2-(*p*-tolylthio)naphthalene-1-ol, **4.4a** (60 mg, 45% yield), yellow viscous oil; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.33 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.82 (dd, *J* = 7.1, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (m, 3H), 7.43 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.26 (s, 1H), 7.06 (s, 4H), 2.29 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.4, 136.2, 135.6, 132.5, 132.0, 130.0, 127.7, 127.6, 127.5, 125.8, 123.9, 120.8, 109.9, 21.0; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 267.0811 (Calculated for C₁₇H₁₄OS + H⁺: 26.0838).

2-((4-Chlorophenyl)thio)naphthalen-1-ol (4.4b)

Pale yellow solid. Yield 69 mg (61%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.32 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.82 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.57 (m, 2H), 7.46 (qt, *J* = 18.8, 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.18 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.15 (s, 1H), 7.02 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.6, 135.8, 134.8, 132.1, 131.8, 129.3, 128.1, 128.0, 127.7, 126.0, 123.9, 123.2, 121.1, 108.6; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 285.0136 (Calculated for C₁₆H₁₁ClOS - H⁺: 285.0135).

2-(Phenylselanyl)naphthalen-1-ol (4.4c)

Pale yellow semi-solid. Yield 51 mg (55%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.34 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.85 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.67 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.57 (m, 2H), 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.22 (m, 3H), 7.11 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.8, 135.8, 133.3, 131.1, 129.51, 129.46, 127.63, 127.55, 126.7, 125.8, 123.5, 123.4, 120.8, 107.6;

4.4.2.5. General procedure for the synthesis of 3-tosyl-1H-indole (4.5a)

A round bottom flask (10 mL) was charged with 3-tosyl-2-oxindole (57 mg, 0.2 mmol), Schwartz reagent, Cp₂ZrHCl (103 mg, 0.4 mmol) in 2 mL of dry THF. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was mixed with ethyl acetate (20 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was extracted with an aqueous saturated solution of sodium chloride or brine solution (5 mL x 2) and water (20 mL x 2). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified over a column of silica gel and eluted with 75:25 hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford 3-tosyl-1H-indole, **4.5a** (35 mg, 63% yield), brown solid; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.45 (bs, 1H), 7.92 (m, 3H), 7.85 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H), 7.43 – 7.40 (m, 1H),

7.29 – 7.23 (m, 4H), 2.37 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 143.5, 140.2, 136.3, 129.8, 129.7, 126.8, 124.0, 123.4, 122.5, 119.4, 116.9, 112.3, 21.5; HRMS-ESI *m/z*: 272.0740 (Calculated for C₁₅H₁₃NO₂S + H⁺: 272.0740).

5-Chloro-1-methyl-3-tosyl-1*H*-indole (4.5b)

Brown solid. Yield 23 mg (60%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.88 (t, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.86 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.71 (s, 1H), 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.21 (s, 2H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 2.34 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 143.5, 140.4, 135.7, 134.4, 129.8, 128.4, 126.7, 125.1, 124.1, 119.3, 115.3, 111.4, 33.8, 21.5 ; LRMS-ESI *m/z*: 320.6 (Calculated for C₁₆H₁₄ClNO₂S + H⁺: 320.1)

Table 4.2: The crystallographic details of compounds **4.1a**

Compound code	4.1a
Molecular formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N O ₃ S
Molecular weight	287.32
CCDC number	1474948
<i>a</i>(Å), <i>b</i>(Å), <i>c</i>(Å), <i>V</i>(Å³)	12.6933(4), 7.6526(2), 15.0369(5), 1334.76(7)
<i>α</i>, <i>β</i>, <i>γ</i> (°)	90, 113.961(2), 90
Crystal System	Monoclinic
Space Group	P 2 ₁ /c
T (K)	296(2) K
Z	4
ρ (g/cm³)	1.430
μ (mm⁻¹)	0.249
F (000)	600
θ min, max (°)	4.819, 28.273
h; k; l (min, max)	-16, 16; -10, 9; -15, 20
No. of reflections	10584
R (int)	0.0349
No. of parameters	182
R₁ all, R₁ obs	0.0468, 0.0381
wR₂ all, wR₂ obs	0.1029, 0.0963
G. F.	1.049

4.5. Representative NMR spectra of chalcogenated oxindoles/heterocycles

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.1a

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.1c

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.21

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.2m

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound 4.2o

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.3a

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.3c

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.4a

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.4c

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound 4.5b

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10. (a) Prasad, C. D.; Balkrishna, S. J.; Kumar, A.; Bhakuni, B. S.; Shrimali, K.; Biswas, S.; Kumar, S. *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 1434. (b) Prasad, C. D.; Kumar, S.; Sattar, M.; Adhikary, A.; Kumar, S. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2013**, *11*, 8036. (c) Kumar, A.; Bhakuni, B. S.; Prasad, C. D.; Kumar, S.; Kumar, S. *Tetrahedron* **2013**, *69*, 5383. (d) Kumar, A.; Kumar, S. *Tetrahedron* **2014**, *70*, 1763. (e) Prasad, C. D.; Verma, A.; Sattar, M.; Kumar, S. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5*, 75881.
11. Compound **4.1a** was crystallized by slow evaporation from chloroform as solvent.
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14. (a) Xu, X.-H.; Wang, X.; Liu, G.-k.; Tokunaga, E.; Shibata, N. *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 2544; (b) Ghosh, S.; Chaudhuri, S.; Bisai, A. *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 1373; (c) Galzerano, P.; Bencivenni, G.; Pesciaioli, F.; Mazzanti, A.; Giannichi, B.; Sambri, L.; Bartoli, G.; Melchiorre, P. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2009**, *15*, 7846.

Appendices

Appendix I: Curriculum Vitae

Myself, Ch. Durga Prasad, from Eluru, a small city from the state of Andhra Pradesh, India. I have completed B. Sc. from Sir C. R. Reddy college, affiliated to Andhra University (2007) and M. Sc. from Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur (2009). In 2011, I have joined the group of Dr. Sangit Kumar, Dept. of Chemistry, IISER Bhopal. He has introduced me to the international scientific fraternity by giving me an opportunity to work in the field of synthetic organochalcogen chemistry. My graduate studies are based on the topic “carbon-chalcogen coupling reactions: synthesis of various chalcogenyl heterocycles”.

Appendix II: Awards and Presentations

- Awarded research fellowship by the University Grants Commission from August 2011- July 2016.
- Presented a talk in the national conference “modern trends in inorganic chemistry-2013”.
- Presented a talk in the internal conference of IISER Bhopal “InTeRaCTiONS-2015”.

Appendix III: Publications

- Prasad, C. D.; Balkrishna, S. J.; Kumar, A.; Bhakuni, B. S.; Shrimali, K.; Biswas, S.; Kumar, S. *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 1434.
- Prasad, C. D.; Kumar, S.; Sattar, M.; Adhikary, A.; Kumar, S. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2013**, *11*, 8036.
- Prasad, C. D.; Verma, A.; Sattar, M.; Kumar, S. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5*, 75881.
- Prasad, C. D.; Sattar, M.; Kumar, S. (manuscript under preparation).
- Balkrishna S. J.; Prasad, C. D.; Panini, P.; Detty, M. R.; Chopra, D.; Kumar, S. *J. Org. Chem.* **2012**, *77*, 9541.
- Kumar, A.; Bhakuni, B. S.; Prasad, C. D.; Kumar, S.; Kumar, S. *Tetrahedron* **2013**, *69*, 5383.
- Kumar, A.; Yadav, A.; Verma, A.; Jana, S.; Sattar, M.; Kumar, S.; Prasad, C. D.; Kumar, S. *Chem. Commun.* **2014**, *50*, 9481.
- Verma, A.; Patel, S.; Meenakshi; Kumar, A.; Sharma, S.; Jana, S.; Yadav, A.; Prasad, C.D.; Kumar, S.; Kumar, S. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 1371.
- Kumar, S.; Rathore, V.; Verma, A.; Prasad, C.D.; Kumar, A.; Yadav, A.; Jana, S.; Sattar, M.; Meenakshi; Kumar, S. *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 82.
- Verma, A.; Jana, S.; Prasad, C.D.; Yadav, A.; Kumar, S. *Chem. Commun.* **2016**, *52*, 4179.
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Ph.D. Thesis

Ch. Durga Prasad

2016